

**A RIGHTS-BASED APPROACH IN ENSURING ENVIRONMENTAL
JUSTICE IN NIGERIA.**

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CERTIFICATION

This is to certify that Joel Odili, with Matric Number 160601530, has written this project under my supervision.

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DEDICATION

This research project is dedicated to God Almighty for his guidance and direction in the course of writing this project, as well as his immense love to me from the time of my birth up until my sojourn in the University of Lagos.

I also dedicate this project to my wonderful and ever supportive family members and my brethren in the Christian faith, which are indeed God's gifts to me.

Lastly, I dedicate this project to victims of environmental abuse who by reason of improper remedies are left to wonder when justice would be served. Your plight is not unnoticed.

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TABLE OF ABBREVIATIONS

AU	African Union
CAMA	Companies and Allied Matters Act
EPA	Environmental Protection Act
EIA	Environmental Impact Assessment
FREP	Fundamental Rights Enforcement Procedure
GHGs	Green House Gases
ICCPR	International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights
ICESCR	International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights
IPCC	Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change
LASEPA	Lagos State Environmental Protection Agency
LAWMA	Lagos State Waste Management Authority
LSEMPL	Lagos State Environmental Management and Protection Law
NAFDAC	National Agency for Food and Drug Administration and Control
NESREA	National Environmental Standards and Regulations Enforcement Agency
NGOs	Non-Governmental Organisation
NHRC	National Human Rights Commission
NOSDRA	National Oil Spill Detection and Response Agency
OAU	Organisation of African Unity
SDGs	Sustainable Development Goals
UDHR	Universal Declaration of Human Rights
UN	United Nations
UNCLOS	United Nation Convention on the Law of the Sea
UNEP	United Nations Environment Programme
UNFCCC	United Nation Framework Convention on Climate Change

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ABSTRACT

Environmental pollution is transboundary, cutting across a large area and can affect an entire community. The affected parties are in most cases left handicapped due to the high threshold in seeking common law remedies and the attendant problems of environmental civil litigation. The statutory framework has done little in ensuring environmental justice in Nigeria. It can be argued that the reason why the problem of environmental pollution persists in Nigeria is due to the attitude of the government, seeking to advance the economy at the cost of a safe and healthy environment. This has been reflected in the gas flaring activities of multinational oil corporations, oil spillage in the Niger delta environs, and the land pollution in various parts of the country, especially Lagos State. Hence, it has become necessary to shift to a rights-based approach in seeking justice for victims of environmental degradation. The rationale behind this approach is that damage done to the environment adversely affects the living conditions of the inhabitants of that environment, leading to an infraction of the right to life. Thus, an attempt would be made to look at the general conception of environmental rights and the employment of the right as a medium for environmental justice especially in Nigeria where the right to environmental protection is non-justiciable. Also, a comparative analysis with India would be examined in order to elicit the best practices adopted in that jurisdiction which are suitable for the Nigerian situation. The research project concludes with recommendations that are geared towards securing the eco-system through the medium of human rights.

CHAPTER ONE

GENERAL INTRODUCTION

1.0. Background of Study

In today's world, society has come to realise that the anthropogenic destruction of our planet's sustainable biodiversity negatively impacts humankind, placing human life at great risk.¹ According to the World Resources' Annual Report 2000-2001, people of all nations, rich and poor, are experiencing the effects of ecosystem decline in one form or another; water shortages, soil erosion, fish kills, landslides on deforested slopes, and fires in disturbed forests are some of the manifestations of environmental degradation that have a direct impact on human beings.² The World Bank observed that more than 850 million persons live in regions affected by desertification. Nearly half a billion persons, mainly women, and children in poor rural areas live in severely polluted environments; 500 million annual premature deaths can be attributed to the high levels of pollution in cities.³ These statistics are justifications for a nexus between human rights and environmental protection.

Environmental degradation leads to a violation of series of human rights like the right to life, the right to dignity of the human person, and the right to health guaranteed under the constitution and international treaties to which Nigeria is a party. In making a case for the right to a clean environment as a basic human right Aditi Singh observed as follows, a healthy environment is an essential aspect of the right to life, not only for human beings but also for other animals on the planet. Violation, therefore, of the right to a healthy environment is potentially a violation of the basic right to life.⁴ This position has been recognised by the Indian Supreme Court's decision in *M.C. Mehta v. Kamal Nath*⁵ where a hotel was discharging effluent into a river and hence causing disturbance to aquatic life and water sanitation. It was held that any disturbance of basic environmental elements namely air, water, and soil which are necessary for life would be hazardous to life and can't be polluted.

In the international arena, the right to the environment was not recognised in the United Nations Charter 1945 which excluded the word 'environment'. However, the nexus between the condition of the human environment and the enjoyment of fundamental human rights was first acknowledged by the United Nations General Assembly towards the end of the 1960s. It was

¹ A. Otubu, "Environmental and Human Rights: An Overview of Current Trends in Nigeria" (2010) *Public Law Journal University of Lagos*, Nigeria 2012.

² UNEP et al, World Resources 2000-2001: People and Ecosystems: The Fraying Web of Life (Washington, D.C., 2001), viii.

³ UNDP, World Development Report, World Bank, and Human Development Report, 1993.

⁴ A. Singh, "Right to Clean Environment: A basic human right" available online at <https://www.legalservicesindia.com/article/1509/Right-to-Clean-Environment:-A-basic-Human-Right.html> (accessed 20 May 2021).

⁵ (1997) 1 SCC 388.

however not until 1972 during the United Nations Conference on Human Environment⁶ that the right to a healthy environment was the major topic of discussion at the global stage which was a response by the United Nations (hereinafter referred to as “U.N.”) to the experiences of citizens around the world to environmental degradation and destruction of natural resources. This created a platform for the constitutional recognition of the right by member states.

Regionally, **the African Charter on Human and Peoples Right** (African Charter)⁷ under its **Article 24** recognises the peoples’ right to a general satisfactory environment suitable to their development. This provision was given effect to by the African Commission on Human Rights in the communication of *The Social and Economic Rights Action Center and the Center Economic, and Social Rights v. The Federal Republic of Nigeria*⁸ in a bid to enforce the environmental right of the Ogoni people.

In the Nigerian context, **section 20 of the Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria**⁹ (hereinafter referred to as “the Constitution”) directs the state to protect and improve the environment and safeguard the water, air and land, forest and wildlife in Nigeria. However, this provision is made non-justiciable by section **6(6)(c) of the Constitution**, so that a victim of environmental degradation would not be able to rely on that provision to enforce his right to a clean and healthy environment. This right, however, could be made enforceable by an enactment rendering the non-justiciable provision justiciable as was done in relation to “corruption”¹⁰ in the case of *Attorney General of Ondo State v. Attorney General of Federation*¹¹ where the Supreme Court decided that the National Assembly could, through the provisions of **Section 4(2) of Constitution** which gives the power to make law for the peace order and good government of any part of Nigeria, legislate on matters within **Chapter II of the Constitution**. Despite the constitutional lacuna created by the non-justiciability of the provision of **section 20 of the Constitution**, the Nigerian court in *Jonah Gbemre v. Shell Petroleum Development Company of Nigeria and 2 others*¹² enforced the environmental right of the members of the Iwehereken community in Delta State Nigeria against the defendants, through the **Fundamental Rights Enforcement Procedure (FREPE) Rules, 2009**. The same was done by the Supreme Court in *Centre for Oil Pollution Watch v. Nigerian National Petroleum Corporation*¹³ where it was held that **Sections 33 and 20 of the Nigerian**

⁶ Declaration of The United Nations Conference on The Human Environment (Stockholm Declaration), 1972 available online at https://legal.un.org/avl/pdf/ha/dunche/dunche_e.pdf (accessed 23 May 2021).

⁷ Adopted by the Organization of African Unity in 1981.

⁸ Communication No. 155/96.

⁹ Cap C23 LFN 2004.

¹⁰ **Section 15(5)** of the Constitution.

¹¹ (2002) 27 WRN 1 SC.

¹² (2005) AHRLR 151 (NgHC 2005).

¹³ (2019) 5 NWLR 518.

Constitution; Article 24 of the African Charter; and Section 17(4) of the Oil Pipelines Act show that the Constitution, the legislature and the African Charter for Human and Peoples' Rights, to which Nigeria is a signatory, recognise the fundamental rights of the citizenry to a clean and healthy environment to sustain life.

Against this backdrop, the project sets out to interrogate environmental protection within the corpus of human rights in the light of trends at the international and regional level as well as in the Indian jurisdiction.

1.1. Statement of Problem

In the quest for economic development, the Nigerian government sought to harness the oil sector of the country, resulting in environmental degradation with a significant impact on the living condition of inhabitants of the Niger Delta environs. Multinational oil corporations like Shell, Chevron, Texaco, Elf, and Eni involved in oil exploration in the country have carried out their operations without due regard to the impact of their activities on the Niger delta environment. The lack of political will on the part of the government to address these problems and the lax environmental laws have led to the oil companies extracting oil and gas with impunity, resulting in violation of human rights and loss of biodiversity.¹⁴ This can also be attributed to the fact that oil accounts for about 90% of Nigeria's foreign exchange earnings.¹⁵

The operations of these multinational oil corporations have worked undue hardship on the inhabitants of the Niger Delta communities. Oil spillage and gas flaring have become normal practices, even though the act of gas flaring has been declared illegal since 1984.¹⁶ Since then, the date for the abolition of gas flaring has changed over the years, and most recently the Senate passed **The Gas Flaring (Prohibition and Punishment) Bill 2020** which provides that "*Any person who flares gas after December 31, 2020, contrary to section 4 of this Act, commits an offence under this Act, and shall be liable on conviction to pay a fine which shall not be less than the cost of gas at the international market.*"¹⁷ Unfortunately, this bill did not see the light of day. At the international level, state parties and oil companies pledged to end gas flaring 2030 under the auspices of the World Bank.¹⁸ The constant change of the date is a clear

¹⁴ G. U. Ojo, PhD and Nosa Tokunbor, "Access to Environmental Justice in Nigeria: The Case for a Global Environmental Court of Justice", *Friends of the Earth International*, October 2016, available online at <https://www.foei.org/wp-content/uploads/2016/10/Environmental-Justice-Nigeria-Shell-English.pdf> (accessed 6 May 2021).

¹⁵ *Ibid.*

¹⁶ The **Associated Gas Reinjection Act**, 1979 stipulates that flaring of gas ceases from 1 January 1984 except with permission from the Petroleum Minister.

¹⁷ Clause 11(a) of the Bill.

¹⁸ Tagged the "Zero Routine Flaring by 2030" initiative, which was introduced by the World Bank, bringing together governments, oil companies, and development institutions who recognise the flaring situation as unsustainable from a resource management and environmental perspective, and who agree to cooperate to eliminate routine flaring no later than 2030. See generally the World Bank publication online at <https://www.worldbank.org/en/programs/zero-routine-flaring-by-2030> (accessed 6 May 2021).

indication that the government does not intend to bring an end to gas flaring activities. This is evident in the fact that none of the statutes that were subsequently enacted were so enacted to curtail the activities of gas flaring. For instance, the **National Environmental Standards and Regulations Enforcement Agency (Establishment) Act** (NESREA) 2007 which is the principal legislation for environmental protection excludes the oil and gas sector from the powers of the NESREA to enforce environmental standard regulations and legislations.¹⁹ The Ogoni people have been the major victim of the adverse effect of gas flaring by oil companies in their community. The Nigeria National Petroleum Corporation recorded that a total of 271.38 billion standard cubic feet of gas, valued at US\$518.33 million was flared in 2015²⁰, in absolute disregard of the no gas flaring policy under the Associated Gas Reinjection Act, 1979.

Gas flaring is just one of the many problems associated with the oil companies' activities, amongst the other problems include oil spillage on land and water. The so-called cleanup process carried out by these companies was a sham, as it did not do enough to restore the environment to its true state. However, it is acknowledged that the restoration of the environment would take a lengthy period.²¹ The United Nations Environment Programme report (UNEP report) 2011 recorded that soil contamination by hydrocarbon was found to a depth of 5 metres in areas purportedly cleaned up by Shell. In one community at *Nisisioken Ogale*, in western Ogoniland, families were discovered to be drinking water from wells contaminated with benzene, a known carcinogen at levels over 900 times above WHO guidelines.²²

From the above events, it is apparent that the laws and institutions put in place to protect the environment have not done enough. Hence Usman puts it thus:

The mere existence of a law seeking to protect the environment does not automatically translate into environmental protection. Some laws are honoured more in breach than in compliance. For a law seeking to protect the environment to actually do so, it must be one that enjoys enforcement in the law courts through the instrumentality of

¹⁹ A. Elebiju, D. Odupe, "Cessations and Destinations: Issues in Gas Flare Commercialization in Nigeria", *LeLaw*, 9 February 2021, available online at https://www.mondaq.com/nigeria/oil-gas-electricity/1034638/cessations-and-destinations-issues-in-gas-flare-commercialisation-in-nigeria#_ftn8 (accessed 6 May 2021).

²⁰ *Supra* note 14.

²¹ The United Nations Environment Programme report (*UNEP report*) 2011 recognised that it would take 25 to 30 years to bring contaminated drinking water, land, creeks and important ecosystems such as mangroves back to full, productive health. Report available online at <https://wedocs.unep.org/bitstream/handle/20.500.11822/8053/-UNEP%202011%20Annual%20Report20121086.pdf?sequence=5&isAllowed=y%2C%20French%7C%7Chttps%3A//wedocs.unep.org/bitstream/handle/20.500.11822/8053/-UNEP%202011%20Annual%20Report-20121086-french.pdf%3Fsequence%3D6&isA=> (accessed 6 May 2021).

²² *Ibid.*

*litigation. If there is no such mechanism then the law, not minding how comprehensive and well couched it is, is nothing but a paper tiger.*²³

To this end, this research project advocates in favour of the Fundamental Rights Enforcement Procedure rules and other human rights mechanism (internationally and regionally) as veritable instruments for environmental protection and justice.

1.2. Research Objectives

The overall objective of this research project is to evaluate the impact of environmental degradation on human rights, and to assess the problems with the current regulatory framework on environmental protection in Nigeria as well as the attendant issues of environmental civil litigation, in order to advocate for a rights-based approach to achieving environmental justice in the light of trends at the international, regional level and in other jurisdictions. Specifically this research aims at the following:

To consider environmental rights in Nigeria and the attitude of the judiciary towards safeguarding the said right. **Section 20 of the 1999 the Constitution** directs the state to protect and improve the environment and safeguard the water, air and land, forest and wildlife in Nigeria. Unfortunately, that provision has been made non-justiciable under **section 6(6)(c) of the Constitution**, so that it is devoid of any legal enforceability. This research aims at showing how that non-justiciable provision can be made justiciable by an enactment, and also to demonstrate the need for the courts to be creative about giving effect to environmental right in light of the fundamental human rights provision and other legal mechanisms pending the time the enactment would be made as was done in the case of *Gbemre v. Shell*.²⁴

To appraise the concept of environmental justice and consider how far Nigeria has gone in realizing the right to environmental protection in the light of contemporary events, courts' decisions and the legislations enacted by the State and Federal government to curb practices that engender environmental degradation.

To compare the enforcement of environmental rights in Nigeria with international and regional instruments and institutions as well as in other jurisdictions. At the international level, environmental issues have been given centre stage on many occasions because of the adverse effect of environmental degradation on the rights to health, to food, to life, and generally the dignity of all human beings. This has been reinforced by the Sustainable Development Goals²⁵

²³ A. K. Usman, "Environmental Protection Law and Practice" Ibadan: *Ababa Press Ltd.*, 2012. p.211.

²⁴ *Supra*.

²⁵ Climate action (Goal 13); Life below water (Goal 14); Life on land (Goal 15).

and the *Vienna Declaration*²⁶ establishing the interdependence of all human rights. The African and European Human Rights institutions have upheld these rights, pursuant to the relevant regional instrument which places an obligation on state parties to realise a safe and healthy environment.

To evaluate the lax legislation on environmental protection and their inefficiency in meeting the end of justice for the victims of environmental pollution. For example, the **NESREA Act, 2007** does not cater for the right to a clean and healthy environment as it offers mere compensation, the **Associated Gas Reinjection Act, 1979**²⁷ that purported to end the flaring of gas from 1 January 1984 was unsuccessful, and the **Environmental Impact Assessment**²⁸ (EIA) **Act** does not address many environmental issues, like gas flaring.

To suggest possible reforms and make recommendations given the Nigerian circumstances in the light of approaches at the international level and other jurisdictions in a bid to solidify this writers' stance on the effectiveness of a rights-based approach in achieving environmental justice in Nigeria.

1.3. Research Question

Flowing from the objectives above, the research question for due consideration in this essay is; How can the rights-based approach be implemented to achieve environmental justice in Nigeria?

1.4. Research Methodology

The method of research shall be doctrinal as relevant legal rules, facts, problems, and gaps shall be thoroughly scrutinized to enable this writer to form opinions and make an evaluation of the subject matter. Also, a comparative research analysis would be employed with India chosen specifically because of the similarity they share with Nigeria to the extent that their constitution only makes environmental rights a state policy²⁹ and not a part of their fundamental human rights, however, the courts in that jurisdiction have upheld environmental rights as an integral part of other human rights, like the right to life.³⁰

1.5. Chapterisation

This project will be divided into five chapters:

²⁶ **Article 5** of the **Vienna Declaration and Programme of Action** of 25 June 1993 (UN Doc. A/CONF.157/24 (Part I), Report of the World Conference on Human Rights).

²⁷ Cap. 20, LFN 2004.

²⁸ Cap. E12, LFN 2004.

²⁹ **Article 48A** on the protection of the environment and **Article 51A** on the fundamental duties of the state towards environmental protection.

³⁰ The Supreme Court of India applied this interpretation in *Rural Litigation and Entitlement Kendra v. Uttar Pradesh*, AIR 1985 SC 652, which is one of their earliest decision on environmental degradation and the ecological balance.

- i. The first chapter is the proposal on the subject matter which states the background of the subject matter, the objectives of the research, and questions sought to be answered by the research;
- ii. The second chapter will discuss the problem of environmental degradation, the concept of environmental justice, as well as the foundation and nature of the environmental right, with the conclusion of a rights-based approach to achieve environmental justice and ;
- iii. The third chapter will examine various regulatory framework on environmental justice in Nigeria, the African Charter, and international treaties in which Nigeria is a party to and the applicability of the right to environmental protection in Nigeria;
- iv. The fourth chapter will undertake a case analysis of environmental justice in Nigeria and a comparative study of India would be carried out in this chapter;
- v. The fifth chapter makes recommendations in the light of international best practices to ensure sustainability of environmental protection through a rights-based approach. The chapter ends with a conclusion of the project research.

CHAPTER TWO

ENVIRONMENTAL JUSTICE WITHIN THE HUMAN RIGHTS CONTEXT

2.0. Introduction

The purpose of this chapter is to evaluate the human rights approach to environmental justice. It has become a well-acknowledged principle of law that where there is a right, there is a remedy (*Ubi jus, ibi remedium*). As a result, victims of environmental degradation would be denied justice unless a legal right³¹ has been established to address the plight of such victims. Against this background, the chapter undertakes the task of looking at the various problems of environmental degradation, and how environmental right was formulated as a reaction to the impact of environmental abuse on the living condition of man, with the ultimate goal of environmental justice for affected parties and the impacted communities. The chapter also appraises the potency of the rights-based approach in achieving environmental justice.

2.1. Problem of Environmental Degradation

The concept of “environmental degradation” is devoid of any universally accepted definition. Many authors and researchers have ascribed meanings to it based on their field of study and research purpose. For instance, Woodwell prefers the term *biotic impoverishment*³² which he described as the systematic destruction of earth’s capacity to support life. Suffice to state that environmental degradation is analogous to environmental pollution. It is said to occur when the earth’s biodiversity is destroyed due to man’s activities in the environment. However, environmental degradation is not a new phenomenon, having been part of human society from time immemorial. However, the difference in modern times is that it has moved from a natural phenomenon to an anthropogenic cause.³³

Environmental degradation can be categorized into the following – atmospheric pollution, marine pollution, and land pollution. Each category would be considered in detail. Atmospheric pollution involves the introduction of anthropogenic substances (like gaseous or other particulate contaminants) into the atmospheric environment, which has the effect of altering the normal balance and affecting the entire ecosystem. The contaminants that affect the atmosphere have been divided into primary and secondary pollutants.³⁴ The primary pollutants

³¹ In this context, reference is being made to an enforceable environmental right.

³² G. M. Woodwell. “The Earth in Transition: Patterns and Processes of Biotic Impoverishment.” *Cambridge University Press; Cambridge, UK*: 1990.

³³ Rashwet Shrinkhal, Chapter 22 - Economics, Technology, and Environmental Protection: A Critical Analysis of Phytomanagement. Phytomanagement of Polluted Sites. Elsevier, 2019. Available online at <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/B9780128139127000223> (accessed 2 June, 2021).

³⁴ Kamala Doršner, “Essentials of Environmental Science”. Available online at <https://openoregon.pressbooks.pub/envirobiology/chapter/10-1-atmospheric-pollution/> (accessed 1 August, 2021).

are those chemicals that directly impact the environment upon their introduction into the atmosphere through human activities,³⁵ while secondary pollutants are produced as a result of a reaction of the primary pollutants with other chemicals in the atmosphere.³⁶ The sources of air pollution can be broadly divided into outdoor³⁷ and indoor sources³⁸.

In more specific terms, one major source of atmospheric pollution is gas flaring during the industrial process. It involves the introduction of Green House Gases (GHGs) in the atmosphere such as methane,³⁹ chlorofluorocarbons, hydrochlorofluorocarbons,⁴⁰ hydrofluorocarbons, methyl chloroform *inter alia*, which damages the ozone layer and opens holes over the Arctic and Antarctic, leaving the earth without any protection from ultraviolet radiation.⁴¹ These gases are also referred to as ozone-depleting substances due to their impact on the ozone layer. Also, not only does the ozone layer get depleted, it ultimately results in climate change. Climate change has been defined under **Article 1(2)** of the 1992 UN **Framework Convention on Climate Change** (UNFCCC), as a change of climate which is attributed directly or indirectly to human activity that alters the composition of the global atmosphere and which is in addition to natural climate variability observed over comparable time periods. It is attributed to be the dominant cause of global warming, according to a recent report released by the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) in 2014.⁴²

Another source of atmospheric pollution is Smog. It is mainly composed of ground-level ozone and particulate matter formed near the troposphere⁴³. It often appears as haze due to the mixture of gases, smoke, and particles. Over the years, smog has proven to harm human health and the environment, as was seen in the *Great Smog of London*,⁴⁴ which covered the city for five days, resulting from the combination of industrial pollution and high-pressure weather conditions. This event led to the death of thousands of persons and cows on the field.⁴⁵ Similarly, in *Trail Smelter Arbitration*⁴⁶ fumes were emitted from Trail Smelter located in British Columbia, which was operated by a Canadian company. The fumes caused damage to the state of

³⁵ Such as, chlorocarbons, methyl chloroforms and Green House Gases.

³⁶ *Supra* note 34.

³⁷ It includes; energy generation, industrial processes, exhaust emissions from vehicles and waste disposals through landfills.

³⁸ Which includes; domestic energy generation (for example, the burning of fire-wood for cooking purposes), secondhand smoke, and sick building syndrome.

³⁹ It is often a by-product in the production of fossil fuels.

⁴⁰ Used in fire extinguishers.

⁴¹ E. W. Chu, J. R. Karr, Environmental Impact: Concept, Consequences, Measurement. Reference Module in Life Sciences, B978-0-12-809633-8.02380-3, (2017). Available online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-12-809633-8.02380-3> (accessed 1 August, 2021).

⁴² Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC), 2014. Summary for policymakers. In: Pachauri, R.K., Meyer, L.A. (Eds.), Contribution of Working Groups I, II, and III to the Fifth Assessment Report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change. Climate Change 2014 Synthesis Report. Geneva: IPCC.

⁴³ The troposphere is the lowest layer of Earth's atmosphere.

⁴⁴ Affected London, England from the 5th of December, 1952 to the 9th of December, 1952.

⁴⁵ Martinez, Julia. "Great Smog of London". Encyclopedia Britannica, 28 Nov. 2020. Available online at <https://www.britannica.com/event/Great-Smog-of-London> (accessed 1 August 2021).

⁴⁶ *United States v. Canada*. Arbitral Trib., 3 U.N. Rep. Int'l Arb. Awards 1905 (1941).

Washington between 1925 and 1937. The United States claimed compensation against Canada for the damage caused. The arbitration found that “under the principles of international law...no state has the right to use or permit the use of the territory in a manner as to cause injury by fumes in or to the territory of another or the properties or persons therein when the case is of serious consequence and the injury is established by a clear and convincing evidence.”

In Nigeria, gas flaring poses as the major source of atmospheric pollution⁴⁷, especially in the Niger Delta region where it has continued unabated since the 5th of June 1956 when oil was found in commercial quantities at Oloibiri, despite the series of laws put in place on various occasions to end the practice.⁴⁸

Marine environmental pollution has been defined under **Article 1(4)** of the U.N **Convention on the Law of the Sea** (UNCLOS), to mean the introduction by man, directly or indirectly, of substances or energy into the marine environment, including estuaries, which results or is likely to result in such deleterious effects as harm to living resources and marine life, hazards to human health, hindrance to marine activities, including fishing and other legitimate uses of the sea, impairment of quality for use of seawater and reduction of amenities. The various sources of marine pollution include; plastic (polythene, plastic bag, bottles, *inter alia*), sewage disposed of in seawater, toxins (from pesticides, fertilizers, phenol, *inter alia*), oil spills, thermal pollutants from power plants, and manufacturing industries.

Another source of marine pollution is ballast water. It is applied to a ship to ensure its stability and safety during voyage, by giving it the balance required to carry out its operations. The impact of ballast water in the marine environment is that certain microscopic organisms and sediments which survive in the ballast tank are later released into the new environment upon discharge of the ballast water. Those organisms act as invasive species and in most cases later become dominant species, leading to the gradual extinction of the native species. The consequences include; public health decline, negative impact on local economies based on fisheries, and similar impacts on local and regional biodiversity.⁴⁹

In addition, eutrophication which is characterized by excessive plant and algal growth leads to the contamination of seafood, resulting in negative impacts on animal and human health⁵⁰. It

⁴⁷ *Gbemre v. Shell (Supra)*.

⁴⁸ According to the U.S State Energy Information Administration, Nigeria is the fifth-largest natural gas flaring country in the world, down from the second position it held in 2011. Gas Flaring: EIA Ranks Nigeria Fifth in the World. Article available online at <https://nairametrics.com/2016/06/02/gas-flaring-eia-ranks-nigeria-as-fifth-in-the-world/> (accessed 3 June 2021).

⁴⁹ H. Buch, “Ballast Water Impacts”. Available online at <https://hansbuch.dk/marine/news/ballast-water-impacts> (accessed 2 August, 2021).

⁵⁰ Some of the diseases resulting from eutrophication include; Paralytic shellfish poisoning (Symptoms: muscular paralysis, difficulty in breathing, shock and in extreme causes death by respiratory arrest); Diarrhoeic shellfish poisoning (Symptoms: diarrhoea, vomiting and

occurs when there is an increased availability of one or more limiting growth factors needed for photosynthesis such as sunlight, carbon dioxide, and nutrient fertilizers.⁵¹

To curb environmental pollution across the world, it is suggested that the principle established in *Trail Smelter's* case could also apply to marine pollution, to the extent that the pollution is of one State's jurisdictional waters from the jurisdictional waters of another State.⁵²

In Nigeria, oil spillage and waste disposal have made immense contributions to the pollution of the marine environment. As a result, clean drinking water and the general livelihood of the habitats are affected, with the reduction of fish catch and farm produce. In *Shell v. Tiebo VII*,⁵³ the plaintiffs sued Shell on behalf of the Peremabiri community for damage from an oil spill. The spill reportedly covered much of the River Nun, a tributary of the Niger, which flows through the plaintiffs' community and provides a source of drinking water. As a result, drinking water was contaminated, and fishing activities were disrupted, *inter alia*.

Land pollution is the introduction of any obnoxious or undesired substance onto the earth, leading to adverse consequences. It occurs when chemicals are deposited on the land in such conditions as to cause injury to man, animals, plants, vegetation, or the aesthetic quality of the physical environment. The sources of land pollution include; Contamination arising from industrial activities (leakage or spillage of materials, the deposition of airborne particles, escape of materials from storage tanks, etc.), Deposit of waste residues (such as landfill sites, industrial effluents, deposits of dredging, the deposit of sewage on agricultural land, etc.), Mining and oil exploration activities (the wastes produced include; well treatment wastes, drill cuttings, oil spillages, hydrocarbon product sludge, etc.).⁵⁴

The consequences of land degradation are; ingestion and inhalation of toxic substances, uptake of contaminants in food, phytotoxicity, flood and erosions, fire and explosion, desertification caused by drought – local food shortage, loss of natural vegetation, and the deterioration of soil. Some of these consequences were experienced in Nigeria following the *Shell-BP Bomu II* blowout of 1970 and *Elf Obagi II* blowout of 1972, which adversely affected agricultural land, salty water, and mangrove swamps in the Niger Delta area.⁵⁵ Similarly, in the case of *Shell*

abdominal pain); Amnesic shellfish poisoning (Symptoms: Mental confusion and memory loss, disorientation and sometimes coma), amongst others. Culled online at http://www.coastalwiki.org/wiki/Possible_consequences_of_eutrophication (accessed 3 August, 2021).

⁵¹ D. W. Schindler, "Recent Advances in the Understanding and Management of Eutrophication", *Limnology and Oceanography* 51, 356-363 (2006). Culled from <https://www.nature.com/scitable/knowledge/library/eutrophication-causes-consequences-and-controls-in-aquatic-102364466/> (accessed 2 August, 2021).

⁵² L. C. Cafilisch, "International Law and Ocean Pollution the Present and the Future". Available online at <http://rbdi.bruiant.be/public/modele/rbdi/content/files/RBDI%201972/RBDI%201972-1/Etudes/RBDI%201972.1%20-%20pp.%207%20C3%A0%2033%20-%20Lucius%20Cafilisch.pdf> (accessed 2 August, 2021).

⁵³ (1996) 4 NWLR (Pt. 445) 657.

⁵⁴ G. O. Amokaye, "Environmental Law and Practice in Nigeria", Lagos: *University of Lagos Press*, 2004. p.246.

⁵⁵ *Ibid.* p.247.

Petroleum Dev. Co. Ltd v. Farah & Ors,⁵⁶ crude hydrocarbons, sulphur, and effluent hazardous chemicals were discharged in thick fountains during the oil blowout, which lasted several weeks. The emissions generated a thick layer over the adjoining land, damaging farmlands, crops, economic trees, and natural vegetation in the impacted areas, resulting in the desertification of around 607 hectares belonging to various families.

From the aforesaid, the various forms of environmental degradation prove costly to the overall wellbeing of humankind, so that when the environment is not adequately protected, the right to life of persons would be of no consequence. It is submitted that if man is aware of the contributions his activities in the environment have on his livelihood, he would refrain from those practices.

2.2. Concept of Environmental Justice

Given the unsustainable use of natural resources in today's world, the distinct ideas of "Environment" and "Justice" have become a necessary admixture. The word "environment" has been defined under **section 37** of **NESREA Act 2007** as including *water, air, land and all plants and human beings or animals living therein and the inter-relationships which exist among these or any of them*. A similar definition is given under **section 61** of the **EIA Act**,⁵⁷ defining it as *the components of the earth' and includes Land, water and air including all layers of the atmosphere; All organic and inorganic matter and living organisms; and the interacting natural systems that include components referred to in paragraphs (a) and (b)*. These definitions limit the environment to the physical environment, failing to capture everything within and around man.⁵⁸

On the other hand, the term "Justice" is elusive.⁵⁹ It has however been defined as implying equity and fairness.⁶⁰ Access to justice can only be realised when some elements of fairness and equity exist in a system to guarantee the realization of basic fundamental rights.⁶¹

The Brundtland Report⁶² represents the first effort to give a conceptual meaning to the term, "Environmental Justice". The report's notion of sustainable development draws together the

⁵⁶ (1995) 3 NWLR

⁵⁷ Cap. E12 LFN 2004.

⁵⁸ A broader definition of environment is given by the Blacks Law Dictionary, 6th ed. (St Paul Minasota: West Printing Co, 1990) as the totality of physical, economic, cultural, aesthetic and social circumstances which surround and affect the desirability and value of property and which also affect the quality of peoples' lives.

⁵⁹ R. W. M. Dias, Jurisprudence (4. ed., Butterworths, 1976), p. 67.

⁶⁰ Socrates equates justice to fairness, while Aristotle in his *Nicomachean Ethics* sees justice as treating equals equally, and unequals unequally.

⁶¹ N. S. Okogbule, "Access to justice and human rights protection in Nigeria: problems and prospects", *Sur, Rev. Int. direitos human.* 2 (3), Dec 2005. Available online at <https://doi.org/10.1590/S1806-64452005000200007> (accessed 5 June 2021).

⁶² Report of the World Commission on Environment and Development: Our Common Future. Available online at <https://sustainabledevelopment.un.org/content/documents/5987our-common-future.pdf> (accessed 5 June 2021).

concern for natural systems' carrying capacity with humanity's social challenges.⁶³ The focus of the report on environmental justice underlies the bold steps recommended for re-examining the problems associated with the critical environment and development inter-linkage and formulating realistic proposals to solve them so as to actualize the aspirational goal of the world community to protect and enhance the environment.⁶⁴

For want of a definition, though not all-encompassing, the United States Environmental Protection Agency (EPA) sees it as the fair treatment and meaningful involvement of all people regardless of race, color, national origin, or income, with respect to the development, implementation, and enforcement of environmental laws, regulations, and policies.⁶⁵ Similarly, Bullard, while analysing the concept opines that environmental justice recognises that environmental costs and benefits are not in a fair and equitable manner and that traditional environmentalism has not been sufficiently concerned with very divergent local situations and the plight of minorities.⁶⁶ Suffice to state that the primary aim of environmental justice is to ensure that every person has an equal degree of protection from environmental hazards.

There are various principles of environmental justice, most of which are derived from the first *National People of Color Environment Leadership summit*⁶⁷. The principles are not watertight as there are instances of overlap. The first of these principles is that mother earth is sacred, everything on earth is connected ecologically and is interdependent, and that every species has a right to freedom from ecological destruction.⁶⁸ It follows that resources in the environment should not be used in such a way that would affect other life forces in the ecosystem. Sadly, this has not been the case in Nigeria especially the Niger Delta environs where oil is extracted by multinational oil companies with impunity. This attitude is a breach of the duty of directors provided under **section 305(3)** of the **Companies and Allied Matters Act (CAMA) 2020**, to act in the best interests of the company as a whole while carrying out its business, so as to preserve its assets, further its business, and promote the purposes for which it was formed, and in such manner as a faithful, diligent, careful and ordinarily skillful director would act in the circumstances and, in doing so, *shall have regard to the impact of the company's operations*

⁶³ K. B. Ejumudo, "The Democracy/Environmental Justice Challenge in Nigeria's Niger Delta and the Developmental Leadership and Governance Culture Imperative" *Journal of Economics and Sustainable Development* www.iiste.org ISSN 2222-1700. Vol.5, No.15 2014, p. 114.

⁶⁴ *Ibid.*

⁶⁵ United States Environmental Protection Agency "Environmental Justice". Available at <https://www.epa.gov/environmentaljustice> (accessed 2 August, 2021).

⁶⁶ R. D. Bullard, "Confronting Environmental Racism: Voices from the Grassroots". London: *Free Press*. (2000).

⁶⁷ Held on October 24-27, 1991, in Washington DC. 17 principles of environmental justice were drafted and adopted. Since then, the principles have served as a defining document for the growing grassroots movement for environmental justice. Available online at http://www.columbia.edu/cu/EJ/Reports_Linked_Pages/EJ_principles.pdf (accessed 2 August, 2021).

⁶⁸ In furtherance to this, *Principle 3* states that Environmental Justice mandates the right to ethical, balanced, and responsible uses of land and renewable resources in the interest of a sustainable planet for humans and other living things.

on the environment in the community where it carries on business operations.⁶⁹ As a principle, Environmental Justice opposes the destructive operations of multinational corporations.

Another notable principle is that Environmental Justice affirms the right of all workers to a safe and healthy work environment without being forced to choose between an unsafe livelihood and unemployment. This principle is reflected in some of the provisions of the **Factories Act**,⁷⁰ especially **section 7(1)** which provides that, “every factory shall be kept in a clean state, and free from effluvia arising from any drain, sanitary convenience or nuisance...” Also, in line with the right to dignity of a human person provided under **section 34(1)(c)** of the **Constitution**, a person shall not be required to perform forced or compulsory labour.

Furthermore, Environmental Justice appeals for the right to participate as equal partners at every decision that needs to be made with regards to their environmental surroundings, including assessment of needs from assessments, planning, implementation, and enforcement. In Nigeria, it is apparent that the members of affected local communities are not considered when decisions affecting their environment are made by the government. This is evident from the failure of the government to consider and give attendance to the plight of the Ogoni people over the gas flaring activities of Shell.⁷¹ As far as assessments are concerned, oil companies have often acted in breach of **section 2** of the **EIA Act**,⁷² which requires an assessment of public or private projects likely to have a significant impact on the environment. In the case of *Gbemre v. Shell*,⁷³ the court held that the failure of the defendants to conduct the mandatory environmental impact assessment concerning their gas flaring activities in the claimants’ community as required by **section 2(2)** of the **EIA Act**, contributed to the unrestrained, mindless flaring of gas by the defendants in the community of the claimants’ which violated their fundamental rights.

Also, Environmental Justice protects the rights of those who fall victim to environmental injustice to receive reparations and full compensation for damages they incur and also receive great health care. From this principle, it would follow that justice delayed would be justice denied. This was the situation in the case of *Shell Petroleum Development Company of Nigeria Limited v. Anaro & Ors*,⁷⁴ which was a 30 years legal battle involving consolidated suits brought for and on behalf of the affected communities (Obotobo, Sokebolo, Ofogbene (Ezon

⁶⁹ The directors of the company would be liable for breach of such duty pursuant to **section 305(9)** of **CAMA 2020**.

⁷⁰ Other relevant provisions include; **sections 9, 12 and 13** dealing with ventilation, sanitary conveniences and duty of inspector as to sanitary defects remediable by local authority (respectively).

⁷¹ According to the United Nations Environment Programme (UNEP) environmental assessment report on Ogoni, 1.8 billion cubic feet of gas is flared daily resulting in about 45.8 billion kW of heat released into the atmosphere. Culled from G. U. Ojo, PhD and N. Tokunbor, *Op. cit.* p.2.

⁷² Cap. E12, LFN 2004.

⁷³ *Supra*.

⁷⁴ (2015) LPELR-24750(SC).

Burutu) and Ekeremor Zion (Ezon Asa) against Shell at the Bendel State High Court in 1995. Following the decision of the Supreme Court in 2015, the appellant was more than happy to oblige to the damages awarded which at this time has reduced significantly in value.

Additionally, Environmental Justice opposes military occupation, repression, and exploitation of lands, peoples, and cultures, and other life forms. Military repression usually manifests in opposition to public demonstrations by environmental activists over the contamination of local communities by oil companies. As a result, armed conflicts and series of violations of fundamental human rights of persons become inevitable. This was the situation in the case of *Wiwa v. Royal Dutch Petroleum Co.*,⁷⁵ the background of which involved the extra-judicial killing of Ken Saro Wiwa on November 10, 1995, and other environmental activists by the then military government in collusion with the defendant, during a peaceful protest. The action was instituted against the defendants⁷⁶ for wrongful death, assault, battery, and series of human rights violations on behalf of the relatives of victims of environmental armed conflicts in Ogoni land.⁷⁷ The defendant opted for out of court settlement on June 8, 2009, involving the sum of \$15.5 million to compensate the plaintiffs, establish a trust for the benefit of the Ogoni people, and cover some of the legal costs and fees associated with the case.⁷⁸

Furthermore, Environmental Justice reconciles environmental concerns with the need to preserve and safeguard human rights by recognizing that everyone has the right to a clean and healthy environment.⁷⁹ In the same vein, it confirms the elementary right to economic, cultural, political, and environmental volition of every person. This right has been recognised in several international human rights instruments. For instance, **Article 25(1)** of the **Universal Declaration of Human Rights 1948** (UDHR) provides that “everyone has the right to a standard of living adequate for the health and well-being of himself and of his family...” Also, **Article 11(1)** of the **International Covenant on Economic Social and Cultural Rights** (ICESCR) ensures the right to the improvement of all aspects of environmental and industrial hygiene. In Nigeria, the need for environmental protection has been recognised under **section 20** of the Constitution, although not expressly guaranteed as a “right”.

⁷⁵ 96 Civ. 8386 (KMW) (HBP), 01 Civ. 1909 (KMW) (HBP), 02 Civ. 7618 (KMW) (HBP) (S.D.N.Y. Mar. 18, 2009). The action was instituted against the Royal Dutch Petroleum Company and Shell Transport and Trading Company for wrongful death, assault, battery and series of human rights violation on behalf of the relatives of victims of environmental armed conflicts in Ogoni land by Center for Constitutional Rights (CCR) and co-counsel from EarthRight International under the Alien Torts Act in United States.

⁷⁶ Royal Dutch Petroleum Company and Shell Transport and Trading Company.

⁷⁷ The Center for Constitutional Rights (CCR) and co-counsel from EarthRight International brought the action under the Alien Tort Claims Act in United States.

⁷⁸ The death of Ken Saro Wiwa saw an increase in the number of environmental rights activists clamouring for environmental justice for the Niger Delta inhabitants, especially the Ogoni people. Since then, over 5000 Ogoni people have been murdered.

⁷⁹ W. P. Cunningham, M. A. Cunningham, and B.W. Saigo, “Environmental science: A Global Concern”. Toronto: *McGraw-Hill*. (2007).

Given the foregoing, environmental justice refers to the fight to improve and maintain a clean and healthy environment, particularly for individuals who have been harmed by pollution in the past. It advocates for equal treatment of all people and meaningful participation in the establishment and enforcement of environmental laws and regulations.

2.3. Foundation and Nature of Environmental Right

The term “Environmental right” is elusive and controversial. It is elusive because there is no universally accepted definition.⁸⁰ Nevertheless, the definition proffered by UNEP is the most suitable for this discourse. The International body defines “environmental right” as any proclamation of a human right to environmental conditions of a specified quality.⁸¹ This definition recognises the qualifications often attributed to environmental rights. Some of those qualifications include the right to a healthy or clean environment, or an environment conducive to well-being and higher standards of living.

The controversial nature of the term stems from the different meanings given to it by the environmentalist and human rights advocates. The former sees it from an ecocentric perspective (environment first) while to the latter it is predominantly anthropocentric (humans first).⁸² Anthropocentric reality sees man as over nature⁸³, while the ecocentric reality equates man to nature.⁸⁴

These dissenting positions can be seen in various international human rights instruments and local legislations in Nigeria. The following provisions support the anthropocentric perspective: **Principle 1** of the **1972 Stockholm Declaration** declares that man has the fundamental right to freedom, equality, and adequate conditions of life, in an environment of a quality that permits a life of dignity and wellbeing; **Article 27** of the **International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights** (ICCPR) provides that, members of minority groups shall not be denied the right, in community with other members of their group, to enjoy their own culture, to profess and practice their own religion, or to use their own language⁸⁵; **Article 24** of the **African Charter on Human and Peoples’ Rights** postulates that all people shall have the right to a general satisfactory environment suitable to their development; **Section 12** of the **Harmful**

⁸⁰ The Lack of consensus as to its definition has led to difficulty of enforcing the right.

⁸¹ UNEP, “What are Environmental Rights”. Accessed online at <https://www.unep.org/explore-topics/environmental-rights-and-governance/what-we-do/advancing-environmental-rights/what> (accessed 2 August, 2021).

⁸² A. Otubu, *Op. cit.* p. 4.

⁸³ The proponents posit that nature exists for man to use and manipulate for his wellbeing, hence protection of the environment should be for the purpose of safeguarding the wellbeing of man.

⁸⁴ The proponents believe that no separation exists between man and nature. To them, damage to the environment is damage to man.

⁸⁵ The U.N. committee on human rights has interpreted this provision in a broad manner, establishing that culture manifests itself in many forms, including a particular way of life associated with the use of land resources, especially in the case of indigenous peoples.

Waste (Special Criminal Provisions) Act⁸⁶ defines the civil liability of any offender. He would be liable to *persons* who have suffered injury as a result of his offending act.

On the other hand, the following provisions support the ecocentric perspective: **Article 12(2)(b)** of the **ICESCR** ensures the right to the improvement of all aspects of environmental and industrial hygiene; **Article 29(1)(e)** of the **Convention on the Right of a Child** provides that the education of the child shall be directed towards the development of respect for the natural environment; **Section 20** of the **Constitution** directs the state to protect and improve the environment and safeguard the water, air and land, forest and wildlife in Nigeria; **Section 72** of the **Nigerian Urban And Regional Planning Act**⁸⁷ provides for the preservation and planting of trees for environmental conservation.

However, Cullet has questioned the relevance of the dissenting opinions especially because environmental law and human rights jurisprudence share similar objectives.⁸⁸ Accordingly, the pervasive influence of local and global environmental conditions on the realization of human rights has deemed it necessary for the condition of the environment to be included in the human rights debate.⁸⁹ As a result of this development, environmental rights are said to consist of the following three:⁹⁰ the right to a clean and safe environment; the right to act to protect the environment; and the right to information, access to justice, and to participate in environmental decision-making.⁹¹

The origin of environmental rights can be traced to the attitude of the Courts in several jurisdictions, applying fundamental human rights provisions as a basis of giving effect to the said right.⁹² This attitude gave rise to the rights-based approach which at the time proved ineffective. With time, world issues relating to the lack of access to fresh water and food supplies necessitated a universal recognition of environmental rights.⁹³ The framework for integrating human and environmental rights was not established until the **Stockholm Conference on the Human Environment** in 1972. That Conference under **Principle 1** declared that man has a fundamental right to freedom, equality, and adequate conditions of life, in an environment of a quality that permits a life of dignity and well-being. In 1992, the UN

⁸⁶ Cap. H1, LFN 2004.

⁸⁷ Cap. N138, LFN 2004.

⁸⁸ They both strive to produce a better condition of life on earth and to tackle universal challenges that must often be solved at the same time at the individual and global level. Specifically, environmental law seeks to protect both nature itself, and for the benefit of humankind on a local and global scale, while human rights looks at the fundamental aspirations of human beings with much more developed compliance mechanisms allowing individuals and groups to claim their rights. Culled from P. Cullet. *Definition of an Environmental Right in a Human Rights Context*, 13 Netherlands Quarterly of Human Rights (1995), p. 25. Available online at <http://www.ielrc.org/content/a9502.pdf>.

⁸⁹ P. Cullet, *Op.cit.* p. 25

⁹⁰ Which embraces both the ecocentric and anthropocentric perspective on environmental protection.

⁹¹ *Supra* note 82.

⁹² *Supra* note 89.

⁹³ *Supra* note 82.

Conference of Rio de Janeiro on Environment and Development (UNCED) formulated a linkage in procedural terms under its **Principle 10**. Rights to information, participation, and remedies to environmental conditions were the central focus of the **Rio Declaration**.⁹⁴ These instruments forged a connection between well-recognised human rights and the quality of the environment.

Notwithstanding this recognition, Otubu argues that its realization would only be achieved when properly articulated with sufficient specificity to permit a tailored remedy.⁹⁵ Consequently, much more must be done domestically by State parties before the rights set out in the International human rights instruments can be fully realised for all people.⁹⁶

In Nigeria, as would be seen much later in a subsequent chapter of this project, though the need for environmental protection has been recognised under **section 20** of the **Constitution**, the provision by virtue of **section 6(6)(c)** of the **Constitution** is devoid of judicial enforcement. However, following the decision of the high court in *Gbemre v. Shell*,⁹⁷ and the subsequent decision of the Supreme Court in *Centre for Oil Pollution Watch v. NNPC*,⁹⁸ environmental rights have become a part and parcel of our law.

On the nature of environmental rights, it is still very uncertain, owing to the several characteristics attributed to it by scholars. It is however clear that environmental protection is intrinsically related to several other human rights and is both a precondition and an outcome to the enjoyment of many rights.⁹⁹ However, Cullet cautioned that environmental right should not be treated as a synthesis right,¹⁰⁰ because it embodies specific characteristics that can be distinguished from other rights, and so does not constitute a ‘shell-right’ aimed at enhancing the realization of the other ones.¹⁰¹

Indeed one of the criticisms levelled against environmental rights is the difficulty of fitting it into any of the categories of human rights.¹⁰² Again, Cullet sounds a note of warning that we cannot and should not attempt to categorize this right as, either a civil and political right (negative right), or an economic, social, or cultural right (positive right), or a solidarity right

⁹⁴ *Supra* note 82.

⁹⁵ *Ibid.*

⁹⁶ Since countries vary in terms of resources, realization of this right would differ based on the resources available. States in the pursuit of realizing the right are advised not to do so at the expense of other rights but in parallel.

⁹⁷ *Supra.*

⁹⁸ *Supra.*

⁹⁹ This is supported by the idea of interdependence of all human rights established under **Article 5** of the **Vienna Declaration and Programme of Action** (*Supra*).

¹⁰⁰ According to Cullet, a synthesis right is a right embodying a number of elements that may also be found in other rights and whose recognition is often seen as a precondition of the enjoyment of all other human rights. They are generally tentacular and imprecise in nature. A good example is the right to development.

¹⁰¹ *Supra* note 89.

¹⁰² Either as a civil and political right, or an economic, social and cultural right.

because it transcends the distinctions and embodies elements found in each of the three categories.¹⁰³ Even at the international level, the right to environmental protection and wellbeing is found both under the **ICCPR**¹⁰⁴ and the **ICESCR**¹⁰⁵ although it appears to tilt more towards the latter as an economic, social, and cultural right. As a result, many nations under their constitution have treated it as a positive right rather than a negative right.¹⁰⁶

Another issue is whether environmental rights can be categorized under individual rights or communal rights. Those who argue that it is an individual right justify their proposition on grounds of the rights of the future generations whose interest must be taken into account but whose individual members cannot be identified.¹⁰⁷ On the other hand, the communal right advocates consider that the environment is not one person's property but the common heritage of the indigenes of the community. This argument usually comes up regarding **Article 24** of the **African Charter**, which employs the word "people". The question this provision poses is, can an individual rely on Article 24 of the African Charter¹⁰⁸ to enforce his environmental rights? In the communication of *The Social and Economic Rights Action Center and the Center Economic, and Social Rights (SERAC) v. The Federal Republic of Nigeria*¹⁰⁹ The African Commission on Human and People's Rights enforced the environmental rights of the Ogoni people. By so doing, treating the right as a communal one.¹¹⁰

This controversy appears to have been laid to rest in Nigeria following the formulation of the **FREP Rules** in 2009 which enjoins the court to give an expansive interpretation to the rights contained under **Chapter IV** of the **Constitution** and the **African Charter**. It is safe to submit that any interpretation of **Article 24** of the **African Charter** other than that which allows an individual to assert his or her environmental rights under the provision would defeat the purpose for which it was made in the first place.¹¹¹

¹⁰³ Environmental rights places an obligation on State parties to refrain from activities harmful to the environment, and enforce policies promoting conservation and improvement of the quality of the environment as well as ensuring that people are protected against environmental risk generated either by governmental or private agencies. Culled from *Supra* note 89.

¹⁰⁴ **Article 27** provides that "members of minority groups shall not be denied the right, in community with other members of their group, to enjoy their own culture, to profess and practice their own religion, or to use their own language." The U.N. Committee on Human Rights has interpreted this provision in a broad manner, establishing culture manifests itself in many forms, including a particular way of life associated with the use of land resources, especially in the case of indigenous peoples.

¹⁰⁵ **Article 11(1)** recognises the right to an adequate standard of living; **Article 12(1)** guarantees the right to the enjoyment of the highest attainable standard of physical and mental health; **Article 12(2) (b)** ensures the right to the improvement of all aspects of environmental and industrial hygiene.

¹⁰⁶ Like India and Nigeria, as well as other third world countries whose governments refuse to include environmental rights as part of the bill of rights provision under their constitution because of the burden it places on a government with little resources to work with.

¹⁰⁷ W. A. Shutkin, "International Human Rights Law and the Earth: The Protection of Indigenous Peoples and the Environment", 31/3 *Virginia J. of Int'l L.* 1991, pp. 479-511, at p. 504.

¹⁰⁸ All people shall have the right to a general satisfactory environment suitable to their development.

¹⁰⁹ Communication No. 155/96

¹¹⁰ The action was brought on their behalf by the applicant against the military government of Nigeria being directly involved in irresponsible oil development practices in the Ogoni region.

¹¹¹ E. F. Okpanachi, "Enforcing Environmental Rights in Nigeria through the Fundamental Rights (Enforcement Procedure) Rules", 2009. Available online at https://www.academia.edu/19835974/Enforcing_Environmental_Rights_in_Nigeria_through_the_Fundamental_Rights_Enforcement_Procedure_Rules_2009 (accessed 16 June 2021).

From the foregoing, environmental right which has been firmly established under international law and most recently in Nigeria was formulated on the premise that the conditions of the environment go a long way in determining the extent to which other rights, especially the right to life, are enjoyed. The nature of the right would depend on the country in question since it cannot be ascertained objectively.

2.4. Rights-Based Approach as a Means to an End of Environmental Justice

The rights-based approach is founded on the belief that environmental degradation harms people's quality of life, their dignity, their protected fundamental human rights, and, ultimately, their ability to achieve long-term development.¹¹² For example, people go hungry or become unwell when the environment is harmed by development projects that destroy land for farming and food production, and their basic human rights are violated.¹¹³ The approach has also become necessary in many jurisdictions due to some factors amongst which are, the long list of defences available to defendants under traditional common law remedies¹¹⁴ and the difficulties associated with those remedies, the lack of political will on the part of the government, and its agencies to enforce laws that curtail environmental degradation¹¹⁵, the high thresholds associated with environmental civil litigation,¹¹⁶ amongst others.

The human rights approach to environmental protection was recognised and affirmed by Vice-President **Justice Christopher Weeramantry**¹¹⁷ of the International Court of Justice in *Gabcikovo-Nagymaros project case*¹¹⁸ where he noted that “the protection of the environment is likewise, a vital part of contemporary human rights doctrine, for it is *sine qua non* for numerous human rights such as the right to health and the right to life itself...as damage to the environment can impair and undermine all the human rights spoken of in the Universal Declaration and other human rights instruments.”¹¹⁹

¹¹² O. Adejonwo-Osho, “The Evolution of Human Rights Approaches to Environmental Protection in Nigeria.” Available online at <https://www.iucnael.org/en/documents/70-adejonwo-osho-the-evolution-of-human-rights-approaches-to-environmental-protection-in-nigeria-1> (accessed 5 July, 2021).

¹¹³ Dr. J. B. Marshall, Barr. F. Bashir, “Human Rights Approach to Environmental Protection in Nigeria: An Appraisal.” *International Journal of Business & Law Research* 8(4):135-147, Oct-Dec., 2020. Available online at <https://seahipaj.org/journals-ci/dec-2020/IJBLR/full/IJBLR-D-12-2020.pdf> (accessed 5 July, 2021).

¹¹⁴ The rule in *Rylands v. Fletcher*, negligence, trespass and public nuisance.

¹¹⁵ This is because economic development is top of the agenda in many countries so that environmental protection has been relegated to a secondary concern of the government.

¹¹⁶ Some of these thresholds include, Requirement of Proving Damages; Burden and Standard of Proof; Establishing a Causal Link between the Damage and the Act; Expert Evidence; Scientific Nature of Environmental Issues; Pre-action notice; Jurisdiction; Locus Standi; Limitation of Action, amongst others.

¹¹⁷ In his separate opinion.

¹¹⁸ *Hung. v. Slov.*, 1997 I.C.J. 7, 88 (Sept. 25).

¹¹⁹ *Ibid.* at 80.

Also, the African Commission on Human Rights adopted the approach in the communication of *SERAC v. The Federal Republic of Nigeria*¹²⁰ to enforce the environmental right of the Ogoni people. It held thus,

“The right to a general satisfactory environment, as guaranteed under **Article 24** of the **African Charter** or the right to a healthy environment, as it is widely known, therefore imposes clear obligations upon a government. It requires the State to take reasonable and other measures to prevent pollution and ecological degradation, to promote conservation, and to secure an ecologically sustainable development and use of natural resources...The right to enjoy the best attainable state of physical and mental health enunciated in **Article 16(1)** of the **African Charter** and the right to a general satisfactory environment favourable to development...already noted, obligate governments to desist from directly threatening the health and environment of their citizens...”

In Nigeria, it was affirmed and applied in *Gbemre v. Shell*,¹²¹ where the court held that the constitutionally guaranteed fundamental rights to life and dignity of human persons provided by **Sections 33(1)** and **34(1)** of the **Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria, 1999** inevitably includes the right to clean poison-free, pollution-free and healthy environment.¹²²

Despite the importance of a rights-based approach in attaining environmental justice, some have questioned its effectiveness due to various factors. The first argument is that environmental rights can only be utilized by human beings to ensure environmental protection so that when environmental degradation does not affect any person, the approach cannot be employed.¹²³ Furthermore, people would only use a rights-based approach if they were personally affected by environmental contamination in a way that they valued. In other circumstances, people may be unaware that environmental harm has occurred.¹²⁴ Similarly, this approach may not be an effective mechanism for environmental damage which affects a particular species which is of no present or potential interest to human beings.¹²⁵ Also, unlike procedural rights like access to information, access to justice, and participatory rights, which

¹²⁰ *Supra*.

¹²¹ *Supra*.

¹²² Also, in *Centre for Oil Pollution Watch v. Nigerian National Petroleum Corporation (Supra)*, the Supreme Court adopted similar approach.

¹²³ T. Madebwe, “A rights-based approach to environmental protection: The Zimbabwean experience” (2015) 15 *African Human Rights Law Journal* 110-128. Available online at <http://dx.doi.org/10.17159/1996-2096/2015/v15n1a5> (accessed 5 July, 2021).

¹²⁴ *Ibid*.

¹²⁵ D. Tladi, “Strong Sustainable Development, Weak Sustainable Development and the Earth Charter: Towards a More Nuanced Framework of Analysis” (2004) 11 *South African Journal of Environmental Law and Policy* 22-24.

can be used to prevent environmental harm, a rights-based approach is typically used as a reaction to environmental harm rather than prevention.¹²⁶

The effectiveness of the rights-based approach can also be hindered by the doctrine of *locus standi*¹²⁷ especially in Nigeria where a strict rule of *locus standi* applies.¹²⁸ However, for the purpose of environmental rights enforcement, the Supreme Court in *Centre for Oil Pollution Watch v. NNPC*¹²⁹ liberalized the concept of *locus standi* by treating environmental rights as a human rights.

Conclusively, the rights-based approach is effective in ensuring environmental justice whether or not the right to environmental protection has been expressly guaranteed under the bill of rights provision in the Constitution of a country because the Court, through an expansive interpretation of other human rights provisions can give effect to it. On the other hand, countries that have environmental rights guaranteed under their Constitution are still required to educate the public about their environmental rights, as right-holders must take action before the rights-based approach can be employed to safeguard the environment. Nonetheless, this approach is not intended to replace the regulatory framework on environmental protection, but to augment it when the latter has been compromised.

2.5. Conclusion

The second chapter of this project was an examination of the subject of environmental degradation given its impacts on the environment and human existence. The chapter also examined the concept of environmental justice and considered some of its principles in the light of the Nigerian situation, with *Wiwa v. Royal Dutch Petroleum Co.* serving as a case study on the consequences of environmental injustice. The chapter further traced the origin of environmental rights and examined its' nature. The chapter concluded with an appraisal of the rights-based approach towards achieving environmental justice.

¹²⁶ B. K. Bucholtz, "Coase and the control of transboundary pollution: The sale of hydroelectricity under the United States-Canada free trade agreement of 1988" (1991) 18 *Boston College Environmental Affairs Law Review* 279.

¹²⁷ *Locus standi* means the right to sue. It has served as an impediment to environmental justice for local communities who due to lack of fund to institute an action require another to do so on their behalf.

¹²⁸ Following **Fatayi-Williams** CJN's hard criterion of *locus standi* formulated in *Senator Adesanya v. President of Nigeria* (1981) All NLR 1, that there must be adequate interest. However, in *Fawehinmi v. Akilu*, (1987) 4 NWLR (Pt.67) 797 **Obaseki JSC** liberalized the *locus standi* rule by applying the "brothers-keeper" principle to public interest and criminal litigation only when the litigant in question has witnessed or reasonably thinks that an offence has been committed. The Supreme Court in the latter case however failed to overrule its earlier decision in *Senator Adesanya*'s case leaving two precedents on the test of *locus standi*.

¹²⁹ *Supra*.

CHAPTER THREE

THE POSITION OF ENVIRONMENTAL RIGHTS IN NIGERIA

3.0. Introduction

Since the Koko incident of 1988,¹³⁰ a series of legislations have been enacted to combat environmental pollution and ensure environmental protection. However, these legislations were fraught with some deficiencies like lack of proper enforcement of the provisions of the law, inadequate fines stipulated, amongst others. Hence, litigants with the help of the Court had to fill this void by relying on their inalienable rights guaranteed under **Chapter IV** of the **Constitution**.¹³¹ Against this background, this chapter seeks to access the various frameworks for environmental rights at the national, regional, and international levels. The chapter also looks at the attitude of the African Commission on Human and Peoples' Rights and other International Human Rights courts in enforcing the right to a clean and healthy environment through the relevant international human rights instrument. The chapter will conclude by considering the non-justiciable provision of **section 20** of the **Constitution** and the Court in Nigeria's approach towards realizing the right to environmental protection.

3.1. National Framework

3.1.1. The Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria 1999 (as amended)

In Nigeria, the need for a safe and healthy environment has been recognised under **section 20** of the **Constitution**, which provides that “*the state shall protect and improve the environment and safeguard the water, air and land, forest and wildlife in Nigeria*”.¹³² In addition, **section 14(2)(b)** of the **Constitution** provides that “the security and welfare of the people shall be the primary purpose of government.” It is said that this provision protects people not only from external attacks but also from the terrible effects of internal upheavals, unemployment, hunger, famine, diseases, ignorance, homelessness, environmental degradation, and pollution.¹³³

¹³⁰ The incident saw the dumping of toxic waste by an Italian company in a remote part of southern Nigeria in June 1988. Due to the pressure of the public on the government, the latter took action through diplomatic means by demanding the Italian government and the company involved to remove the toxic waste. As a matter of emergency, the then military government enacted the **Harmful Waste (Special Criminal Provisions) Act, 1988** Cap. H1, LFN 2004.

¹³¹ This is because **section 20** of the **Constitution** is non-justiciable, and so cannot be enforced in a court of competent jurisdiction.

¹³² This provision is reinforced by **section 17(1)(d)** of the **Constitution** which states that, *In furtherance of the social order – exploitation of human or natural resources in any form whatsoever for reasons, other than the good of the community, shall be prevented.*

¹³³ Dr. A. O. Bello, “Right to a Clean Environment”, *Environmental Law Lecture note*, University of Lagos 2021. p.4.

However, the above provisions by virtue of **section 6(6)(c)** of the **Constitution**¹³⁴ are non-justiciable,¹³⁵ thereby rendering the constitutional recognition of a clean environment a toothless bulldog.¹³⁶ Another argument against these provisions (especially **section 20**), as a tool for environmental protection, can be found under the *theory of the Jural Relations of Hohfeld*,¹³⁷ where he posited that a right can only be regarded as such when there is a correlative duty placed on another person (including a State) to realise the right. Hence, the fact that persons are not able to enforce this provision in a Court of law is evidence of its inapplicability as a “right”.

Notwithstanding the above, the provision of **section 13** of the **Constitution** states that “*It shall be the duty and responsibility of all organs of government, and of all authorities and persons, exercising legislative, executive or judicial powers, to conform to, observe and apply the provisions of this chapter of this Constitution.*”¹³⁸ Hence, though **section 13** falls under the ambit of **section 6(6)(c)** of the **Constitution**,¹³⁹ the executive and the legislative arm of government still have an obligation under that section to conform to, observe and apply the provisions of chapter II, which includes **section 20** of the **Constitution**.¹⁴⁰

Furthermore, the right to life and the right to dignity guaranteed under **sections 33** and **34** of the **Constitution** has often been treated as mediums for securing a safe and healthy environment, since the damage done to the environment can endanger the lives of human beings and ultimately reduce the quality of their lives. **Section 33(1)** and **(2)** of the **Constitution** states the various grounds for which a person may be deprived of his life, namely: *in the execution of the sentence of a court; in the defence of any person from unlawful violence or for the defence of property; to effect a lawful arrest or to prevent the escape of a person lawfully detained; or to suppress a riot, insurrection or mutiny.* From this section, the various

¹³⁴ That section provides that, “*The judicial powers vested in accordance with the foregoing provision of this Section shall not, except as otherwise provided by this constitution, extend to any issue or question as to whether any Act or omission by any authority or Person or as to whether any Law or any Judicial Decision is in Conformity with the Fundamental Objectives and Directive Principles of State Policy set out in Chapter II of this Constitution.*”

¹³⁵ The Federal Government of Nigeria in the Communication of *SERAC v. Nigeria* (Supra), unsuccessfully sought to rely on the non-justiciability of the provision of **section 20** of the **Constitution** as a defence for their failing to carry out their obligation of safeguarding the environment of the Ogoni people against the incessant pollution of the said environment by oil companies.

¹³⁶ *Supra* note 2.

¹³⁷ He treated right and duty as *jural* correlatives, which means the relationship others have with a person seized with such right. W.N. Hohfeld, “Fundamental Legal Conceptions as Applied in Judicial Reasoning”, *The Yale Law Journal*, vol. 26, no. 8, 1917, pp. 710–770. JSTOR, www.jstor.org/stable/786270 (accessed 16 July, 2021).

¹³⁸ In addition, duties have been placed on the citizens by virtue of **section 24(d)** and **(e)** of the **Constitution** *to make positive and useful contributions to the advancement, progress and well-being of the community where he resides; and render assistance to appropriate and lawful agencies in the maintenance of law and order.*

¹³⁹ The Court of appeal in *Archbishop Okogie v. the Attorney-General of Lagos State* (1981) 2 NCLR 337 at 340-350, held that **section 13** of the **Constitution** has not made **Chapter II** of the **Constitution** justiciable in the light of **section 6(6)(c)** of the same Constitution that ensures that no court has jurisdiction to pronounce any decision as to whether any organ of government has acted or is acting in conformity with the Fundamental Objectives and Directive Principles of State Policy.

¹⁴⁰ C. T. Emejuru, “Human Rights and Environment: Whither Nigeria?” *Journal of Law, Policy and Globalization* www.iiste.org ISSN 2224-3240 (Paper) ISSN 2224-3259 (Online). Vol.35, 2015. Available online at https://www.researchgate.net/publication/271211846_Human_Rights_and_Environment_Whither_Nigeria (accessed 16 July, 2021).

grounds for which a person's life may be deprived do not include environmental use or the process of industrialization geared towards economic growth and development.¹⁴¹

Hence, a multinational oil corporation cannot hide behind the mask of community development to justify the damage caused to the environment of local communities especially their air space as a result of the gas flaring activities of that corporation. In the case of *Jonah Gbemre v. Shell*¹⁴², the provisions of **sections 33(1) and 34(1) of the Constitution** were utilized by the applicant through the **FREP Rules 2011** to enforce the right to a clean, poison-free, pollution-free, and healthy environment of members of the Iwehereken community in Delta State Nigeria. **Judge Nwokorie** decided that the actions of the 1st and 2nd Respondent in continuing to flare gas in the course of the oil exploration and production activities in the Applicant's community is a violation of their fundamental right to life (including a healthy environment) and dignity of human persons guaranteed by the Constitution and the African Charter.

Also, in a more recent decision of the Supreme Court in the case of *Centre for Oil Pollution Watch v. Nigerian National Petroleum Corporation*,¹⁴³ **Kere-Ekun JSC** held that **Sections 33 and 20 of the Nigerian Constitution; Article 24 of the African Charter; and Section 17(4) of the Oil Pipelines Act**¹⁴⁴ show that the Constitution, the legislature and the African Charter for Human and Peoples' Rights, to which Nigeria is a signatory, recognise the fundamental rights of the citizenry to a clean and healthy environment to sustain life.

3.1.2. Federal and State Environmental Legislation

Over the years, various legislations have been put in place by the government for the protection of the environment. These legislations help to supplement the right to the environment. Albeit, issues have emanated from them. The first issue is as regards the legislative competence of environmental matters, which stems from the fact that the word "environment" is excluded from both the exclusive and concurrent legislative list under the constitution¹⁴⁵, making it a residual matter to be exclusively legislated upon by the State.¹⁴⁶ However, some scholars¹⁴⁷ have argued that the various legislations passed by the National Assembly concerning the

¹⁴¹ Also, **section 34(1)(a) of the Constitution** which states that no person shall be subjected to torture or inhuman or degrading treatment. It is an inhuman treatment to flare gas in absolute disregard of the well-being of members of the community.

¹⁴² *Supra*.

¹⁴³ *Supra*. 587 and 597.

¹⁴⁴ Cap. 7 LFN 2004. That section provides that, "Every licence shall be subject to the provisions contained in this Act as in force at the date of its grant and to such regulations concerning public safety, the avoidance of interference with works of public utility in, over and under the land included in the licence and **the prevention of pollution of such land or any waters as may from time to time be force.**" (Emphasis added).

¹⁴⁵ Second Schedule, Part I and II of the 1999 Constitution (as amended).

¹⁴⁶ This could be read into the provision of **section 4(7)(a) and (b) of the Constitution**. In 2017, Lagos state took advantage of these provisions and enacted the **Lagos State Environmental Management and Protection Law**, which is the most comprehensive piece of legislation on the environment made by any State legislature in the federation.

¹⁴⁷ G. O. Amokaye, *Environmental Law and Practice in Nigeria*, Lagos: *Op. cit.* p.130.

environment can be justified by the concurrent powers given to both the Federal and State legislative organ,¹⁴⁸ as well as **item 16** under the exclusive legislative list.¹⁴⁹

In relation to the question of conflict between the state and federal legislation, it is settled law that when the federal legislation has governed a particular field, the state law cannot operate and where it was in operation before the enactment of the federal legislation, that state law would be in abeyance till the federal legislation ceases to exist.¹⁵⁰ However, where the federal law does not cover the field, the state law would operate to fill the gap left by the federal legislation.¹⁵¹ It is submitted that the **NESREA Act 2007**¹⁵² which is the most comprehensive legislation on the protection of Nigeria's environment did not cover the field but affords states and local governments the opportunity of adopting guidelines made by the agency after due consultation has been made with the relevant local and state bodies. In the absence of a guideline made by the agency, the State and local government councils may set up a guideline that suits their local circumstances.¹⁵³

Another issue is that most of the laws are not essentially environmental but merely contain haphazard environmental protection provisions.¹⁵⁴ For instance, **sections 245 and 247** of the **Criminal Code**¹⁵⁵ deal with offences ranging from fouling water, to the use of noxious substances; **Section 13** of the **Factories Act**¹⁵⁶ allows an inspector to take emergency measures or request that emergency measures be taken by a person qualified to do so in cases of pollution or any nuisance. Similarly, some laws are geared only towards a particular environmental hazard with the exclusion of others. For instance, the focus of the **Nuclear Safety and Radiation Protection (NSRP) Act**¹⁵⁷ is to protect the environment from the harmful effects of ionizing radiation¹⁵⁸; while that of the **National Oil Spill Detection and Response Agency**

¹⁴⁸ For instance, **item 17** gives the national legislature powers to make laws inter alia for the Health, Safety, and welfare or the interstate transportation and commerce, and **item 18** gives the state legislature power to make laws for a state with respect to industrial, commercial, or agricultural development of the states.

¹⁴⁹ It includes "Defence" as a part of the exclusive legislative competence of the National assembly. This item has been used to justify the provisions of the **Harmful Wastes (Special Criminal Provisions etc.) Act** Cap. H1, LFN 2004, which was enacted to ward off dumping of hazardous wastes by external forces.

¹⁵⁰ B.O. Nwabueze, *Federalism in Nigeria under the Presidential Constitution* (Sweet & Maxwell 1983) page 63.

¹⁵¹ Pursuant to **section 4(5)** of the **Constitution**.

¹⁵² This Act replaced the **Federal Environmental Protection Agency Act** (FEPA), 1988. Cap. 131 LFN 1990. Some noteworthy provisions of **NESREA Act 2007** on environmental protection include: **Section 7** which provides authority to ensure compliance with environmental laws, local and international, on environmental sanitation and pollution prevention and control through monitor and regulatory measures. **Section 8(1)(k)** which empowers the Agency to make and review regulations on air and water quality, effluent limitations, control of harmful substances and other forms of environmental pollution and sanitation. **Section 27** which prohibits, without lawful authority, the discharge of hazardous substances into the environment.

¹⁵³ **Section 1(2)** of the **NESREA Act** provides that, the Agency, shall, subject to the provisions of this Act, have responsibility for the protection and development of the environment, biodiversity conservation and sustainable development of Nigeria's natural resources in general and environmental technology, including coordination and liaison with relevant stakeholders within and outside Nigeria on matters of enforcement of environmental standards, regulations, rules, laws, policies and guidelines. (Emphasis added).

¹⁵⁴ *Supra* note 147.

¹⁵⁵ Cap. C38 LFN 2004

¹⁵⁶ Cap. F1 LFN 2004

¹⁵⁷ Cap. N142 LFN 2004.

¹⁵⁸ **Section 4** of the **NSRP Act**.

(NOSDRA) (Establishment) Act¹⁵⁹ is on oil activities; and that of the **Associated Gas Re-Injection Act** is on the gas flaring activities of oil and gas companies in Nigeria.¹⁶⁰

The last issue to be examined is the question of *mensrea*¹⁶¹ concerning those offences created under environmental legislation. Most of the provisions leave no room to consider the intention of the accused person, hence creating a strict liability offence.¹⁶² Though there is a presumption of the existence of a mental element in common law jurisdictions when the provision is silent on any mental element,¹⁶³ this presumption could be rebutted from the general intent of the Act.¹⁶⁴ If mental elements were to be read into provisions that were silent on it, many environmental offences would go unpunished.¹⁶⁵

From the foregoing, Nigeria is yet to have a uniform and comprehensive legislation on environmental protection that sufficiently serves the needs of all stakeholders in the country and addresses all vital issues affecting our ecosystem. Hence, it is submitted that these legislations should be consolidated to avoid instances of overlapping functions of agencies or conflicting provisions. Uniform environmental legislation would help reinforce the environmental rights of persons recognised under the constitution.

3.2. Regional Framework: The African Charter on Human and Peoples' Rights

The **African Charter** is an important human rights instrument for Nigeria because it contains most of the economic and social rights under **Chapter II** of the **Constitution**. The Charter was adopted by the Organisation of African Unity (OAU) in 1981,¹⁶⁶ and Nigeria was amongst the signatories to the Charter. It was subsequently passed into law by an enactment of the National Assembly pursuant to **section 12(1)** of the **Constitution**¹⁶⁷ and became known as the **African**

¹⁵⁹ **Section 6** of the NOSDRA Act lists the functions of the Agency to include: Responsibility for surveillance and compliance with all environmental legislation and the detection of oil spills in the petroleum sector; and Encouraging regional co-operation among the member states of the West-African sub-region and the Gulf of Guinea to combat oil spillage in Nigeria's contiguous waters.

¹⁶⁰ **Section 3(1)** of the Act prohibits, without lawful permission, any oil and gas company from flaring gas in Nigeria.

¹⁶¹ The general rule under criminal law is that for a person to be guilty of an offence, the prosecution must discharge the burden of proving both the physical element (*actus reus*) and the mental element of the offence (*mensrea*). This rule is encapsulated in the maxim, "*actus non facit reum, nisi mens sit rea*".

¹⁶² For instance, **section 1(2)** of the **Harmful Wastes Act** provides that any person who, without lawful authority – carries, deposits, dumps, or causes to be carried, deposited or dumped...any harmful wastes on land...shall be guilty of a crime. This provision creates a strict liability against the person who carries out any of the proscribed acts. However, some scholars have argued that the word "causes" employed under the section would suggest a degree of knowledge required on the part of the person when carrying out the Act. This argument is erroneous because a person may "cause" a result without being aware of the consequences of his act. J. K. Odwo-Bentil, *Environmental Pollution Control and Strict Liability in Anglo-Australian Penal Law*, pp. 255 at 257. Culled from *Supra* note 147.

¹⁶³ In Southern Nigeria, this presumption is founded on the provision of **section 24** of the **Criminal Code** which is the general provision of the requirement of mental element.

¹⁶⁴ *Supra* note 147.

¹⁶⁵ According to **Lord Salmon** in *Alphacell Ltd. v. Woodward*, (1972) A.C. 824 the offences "are not criminal in any real sense but are acts which in the public interest are prohibited under a penalty..."

¹⁶⁶ Now known as the African Union (AU).

¹⁶⁷ It provides that, "No treaty between the Federation and any other country shall have the force of law except to the extent to which any such treaty has been enacted into law by the National Assembly."

Charter on Human and Peoples' Rights (Ratification and Enforcement) Act.¹⁶⁸ Hence, the Charter is part of our municipal order and has the same legal force as any other enactment.¹⁶⁹

The relevant provision of the **African Charter** to environmental right is **Article 24**, which provides that *all people shall have the right to a general satisfactory environment suitable to their development*. This provision came up for consideration before the African Commission on Human and Peoples' Rights in the Communication of *The Social and Economic Rights Action Center and the Center Economic, and Social Rights v. Federal Republic of Nigeria*.¹⁷⁰ The Commission gave a broad interpretation to the above provision in a bid to enforce the right to a clean and healthy environment. The brief facts of this communication were that, in March 1996, the petitioners filed a complaint alleging series of violations of the human rights of the Ogoni people. The communication alleged that the Military Government of Nigeria had been directly involved in irresponsible oil development practices in the Ogoni region. In particular, the complaint expressed strongly the widespread contamination of soil, water, and air; the destruction of homes; the burning of crops and killing of farm animals; and the climate of terror the Ogoni communities had been suffering of, in violation of their rights to health, a healthy environment, housing, and food. The applicant alleged, *inter alia*, that such acts constituted violations of the rights to health and a clean environment under **Articles 16** and **24**, respectively, of the African Charter on Human and Peoples' Rights.

The Commission found, *inter alia*, that Nigeria violated **Article 16** (right to health) and **Article 24** (right to a clean environment) of the Charter. The Commission recognised the link between a clean and safe environment and the quality of life and safety of the individual. Moreover, the Commission underscored that the right to health and the right to a clean environment requires that states take the necessary measures to protect the environment and the health of people.

Similarly, the Economic Community of West African States (ECOWAS) Court of Justice in the case of *Socio-Economic Rights and Accountability Project (SERAP) v. Federal Republic Nigeria*¹⁷¹ relied on the provisions of **Articles 1**¹⁷² and **24** of the **African Charter**. The facts of this case were that SERAP, a non-governmental organisation, filed a case against the Federal Republic of Nigeria alleging human rights violations and environmental degradation as a result of lack of effective clean-up exercise of impacted sites in the Niger Delta caused by oil spillage.

¹⁶⁸ Cap. 10 LFN 1990 (now Cap. A9 LFN 2004).

¹⁶⁹ In the case of *Abacha v. Fawehinmi* (2001) 51 WRN 29 the Supreme Court per **Ejiofor JSC** held that "The Africa Charter on Human and Peoples' Rights, having been passed into our municipal law, our domestic courts have certainly the jurisdiction to construe or apply the treaty. It follows then that anyone who felt that his rights as guaranteed or protected by the Charter, have been violated could well resort to its provisions to obtain redress in our domestic courts".

¹⁷⁰ *Supra*.

¹⁷¹ Judgment N° Ecw/Ccj/Jud/18/12.

¹⁷² It provides that, *member states are required to recognise the rights enshrined in the Charter and to adopt legislative or other measures to give effect to these rights*.

SERAP claimed that the Nigerian government's failure to effectively enforce environmental protection measures in these circumstances violates its international human rights obligations under the ICESCR, the ICCPR, and the African Charter.

In the governments' defence it was argued that the applicant (SERAP) lacked *locus standi* to institute the action and that the Court did not have jurisdiction to rule on alleged violations of the ICESCR or the ICCPR. The basis of this defence was that the applicants' claims were founded on mere policy directives under the country's Constitution and consequently were not enforceable.

The Court however held that “...*the sources of Law that the Court takes into consideration in performing its mandate of protecting Human Rights are not the Constitutions of Member States, but rather the international instruments to which these States voluntarily bound themselves at the international level, including the Universal Declaration of Human Rights, the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights, the International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights and the African Charter on Human and Peoples' Rights....once the concerned right for which the protection is sought before the Court is enshrined in an international instrument that is binding on a Member State, the domestic legislation of that State cannot prevail on the international treaty or covenant, even if it is its own Constitution.*”

On this premise, the Court found that the Federal Republic of Nigeria had violated **Articles 1** and **24** of the **African Charter** by their failure to protect the Niger Delta environment from degradation. Furthermore, the Court held that when viewed together, **Articles 1** and **24** impose a positive obligation on the Member States to take every measure necessary to maintain the quality of the environment, such that it can satisfy the human inhabitants and enhance their sustainable development. Although the Nigerian government had taken some legislative measures to respond to the environmental situation in the Niger Delta, the Court held that, in practice, these measures were insufficient to prevent the continued environmental degradation of the region.

In Nigeria, the African Charter was employed by the Supreme Court per **Eko JSC** to guarantee environmental rights in *Centre for Oil Pollution Watch v. Nigerian National Petroleum Corporation*,¹⁷³ where the Court relying on **Articles 24** and **20** of the **African Charter**, held

¹⁷³ *Supra*. 598

that as long as Nigeria remains a signatory to the African Charter, and other global as well, the Nigerian courts would protect and vindicate human rights entrenched therein.

Flowing from the above, the right to environmental protection has been well entrenched and enforced at the regional level by virtue of the provisions of the African Charter. The decision of the regional human rights commission/court demonstrates that to justify a non-accountable government on grounds of non-justiciability of the **Chapter II** provisions under the **Constitution** is baseless.

3.3. International Framework

Historically, environmental right was not considered as one that could endanger human life by the United Nation in 1945 when the **U.N. charter** was signed by member states as the charter in its totality excludes the word ‘environment’.¹⁷⁴ The nexus between the condition of the human environment and the enjoyment of fundamental human rights was first acknowledged by the **U.N. General Assembly** on 3rd December 1968.¹⁷⁵ It was however not until 1972 during the **U.N. Conference on the Human Environment** in Stockholm that the right to a healthy environment was the major topic of discussion on a global stage.¹⁷⁶ **Principle 1** of the Conference declared that man has a fundamental right to freedom, equality, and adequate conditions of life, in an environment of a quality that permits a life of dignity and well-being and he bears a solemn responsibility to protect and improve the environment for present and future generations. It is argued that the above provision is merely an indirect recognition of a right to a healthy environment, by establishing a link between well-recognised human rights, such as the right to freedom and the right to life, and the quality of the environment.¹⁷⁷

In course of time, the U.N. realised that environmental protection and economic development needed to be reconciled because developing countries were concerned that environmental protection would take precedence over economic development.¹⁷⁸ As a result, in 1992, the **U.N. Conference on Environment and Development** held in Rio de Janeiro produced **Principle 1**, which stated that “*Human beings* are at the centre of concerns for *sustainable development*. They are entitled to a healthy and *productive life* in harmony with nature.”¹⁷⁹ Rather than

¹⁷⁴ The U.N. Charter is available online at <https://www.un.org/en/about-us/un-charter/full-text>. (Accessed 20 July, 2021).

¹⁷⁵ The 1733rd preliminary meeting of the General Assembly, 3 December 1968. Available online at [https://undocs.org/en/A/RES/2398\(XXIII\)](https://undocs.org/en/A/RES/2398(XXIII)). (Accessed 20 July, 2021)

¹⁷⁶ United Nations Conference on the Human Environment, 5-16 June 1972, Stockholm. Available online at <https://www.un.org/en/conferences/environment/stockholm1972> (accessed 20 July, 2021).

¹⁷⁷ M. Déjeant-Pons, M. Pallemarts, “Human Rights and the Environment”, *Council of Europe*, June 2002, p. 11. Available online at <https://rm.coe.int/1680489692> (accessed 20 July, 2021).

¹⁷⁸ *Ibid.*

¹⁷⁹ Emphasis added.

affirming individual environmental rights, the major goal of this provision is to articulate an anthropocentric rationale for environmental protection and sustainable development.¹⁸⁰

Worthy of note is the **U.N Sustainable Development Goals** (SDGs) program which incorporated the following environmental issues as part of its goals; climate action (Goal 13); life below water (Goal 14); life on land (Goal 15). State parties have an obligation to fulfil, respect, promote and protect the goals.¹⁸¹

The right to environmental protection has been generally recognised (though not expressly guaranteed) under several international human rights instruments. For instance, **Article 25(1)** of the **UDHR** provides that “everyone has the right to a standard of living adequate for the health and well-being of himself and of his family...” Similarly, the **ICESCR** under **Article 11(1)** recognises the right to an adequate standard of living; **Article 12(1)** of the **Covenant** guarantees the right to the enjoyment of the highest attainable standard of physical and mental health; **Article 12(2)(b)** of the **Covenant** ensures the right to the improvement of all aspects of environmental and industrial hygiene. The Committee on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights in its *General Comment 12*¹⁸² on the Right to Adequate Food¹⁸³ interpreted **Article 11** of the **Covenant** to mean that the State must adopt food safety and other protective measures to prevent contamination through bad environmental hygiene. Similarly, *General Comment 4* on the right to adequate housing by the Committee interpreted **Article 11(1)** to mean that, housing should not be built on polluted sites nor in proximity to pollution sources that threaten the right to health of the inhabitants.¹⁸⁴

Also, **Article 27** of the **ICCPR** provides that “members of minority groups shall not be denied the right, in community with other members of their group, to enjoy their own culture, to profess and practice their own religion, or to use their own language.” In its *General Comment* on CCPR, the Human Rights Committee gave a broad interpretation to the above provision, establishing that culture manifests itself in many forms, including a particular way of life associated with the use of land resources, especially in the case of indigenous peoples. The

¹⁸⁰ *Supra* note 177.

¹⁸¹ The SDGs, also known as the Global Goals, were adopted by 193 Countries at the Sustainable Development Summit in Rio de Janeiro in 2012. Hence, based on the principle of *pacta sunt servanda*, state parties that have committed to these goals are bound by it under international law.

¹⁸² General comment is a **treaty body's interpretation of human rights treaty provisions**, thematic issues or its methods of work. General comments often seek to clarify the reporting duties of State parties with respect to certain provisions and suggest approaches to implementing treaty provisions. Culled online from <https://ask.un.org/faq/135547#:~:text=General%20comment%20is%20a%20treaty,approaches%20to%20implementing%20treaty%20provisions> (accessed 20 July, 2021).

¹⁸³ CESCR General Comment No. 12: The Right to Adequate Food (Art. 11) Adopted at the Twentieth Session of the Committee on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights, on 12 May 1999 (Contained in Document E/C.12/1999/5). Available online at <https://www.refworld.org/pdfid/4538838c11.pdf> (accessed 20 July, 2021).

¹⁸⁴ CESCR General Comment No. 4: The Right to Adequate Housing (Art. 11 (1) of the Covenant) Adopted at the Sixth Session of the Committee on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights, on 13 December 1991 (Contained in Document E/1992/23). Available online at <https://www.refworld.org/pdfid/47a7079a1.pdf> (accessed 20 July, 2021).

committee stated that the enjoyment of this right may require positive legal measures of protection and measures to ensure the effective participation of members of minority communities in decisions that affect them. The committee also noted that the State's obligation to protect the right to life includes positive measures designed to reduce infant mortality and protect against malnutrition and epidemics.¹⁸⁵

In the communication of *EHP v. Canada*¹⁸⁶ brought before the U.N. Human Rights Committee, a group of Canadian citizens alleged that the storage of nuclear waste near their homes threatened the right to life of present and future generations. The Committee found that the case raised serious issues concerning the obligation of State parties to protect human life, but declared the case inadmissible due to failure to exhaust local remedies.

Also, in *Bordes and Temeharo v. France*,¹⁸⁷ the Committee found the case inadmissible on the ground that the claimants did not qualify as victims of a violation. The communication concerned France's nuclear tests among the atolls of Mururoa and Fangataufa in the South Pacific. The Committee seemed concerned with the remoteness of the harm. Applicants claimed that the tests represented a threat to their right to life and their right not to be subjected to arbitrary interference with their privacy and family life. They attempted to place the burden of proof on the government, contending that French authorities had been unable to show that the tests would not endanger the health of the people living in the South Pacific or the environment by further damaging the geological structure of the atolls. The Committee held that the applicants had not substantiated their claim that the tests had violated or threatened violation with the rights invoked. As for their contention that the tests increased the likelihood of a catastrophic accident, the Committee notes that this contention is highly controversial even in concerned scientific circles; the Committee can't ascertain its validity or correctness. Thus, the lack of scientific certainty coupled with the burden of proof on the applicants limited the claimants' ability to obtain relief through human rights proceedings.

Furthermore, in more specific terms concerning a child **article 29(1)(e)** of the **Convention on the Right of a Child** ensures that the education of the child shall be directed towards the "development of respect for the natural environment."¹⁸⁸ Also, **article 24(2)(c)** of the

¹⁸⁵ General Comment Adopted by the Human Rights Committee under Article 40, Paragraph 4, of the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights, CCPR/C/21/Rev.1/Add.5 26 April 1994. Available online at https://tbinternet.ohchr.org/_layouts/15/treatybodyexternal/Download.aspx?symbolno=CCPR%2fC%2f21%2fRev.1%2fAdd.5&Lang=en. (accessed 20 July, 2021).

¹⁸⁶ Communication No. 67/1980, U.N. Doc. CCPR/C/OP/1 at 20 (1984).

¹⁸⁷ Communication No. 645/1995, U.N. Doc. CCPR/C/57/D/645/1995 (1996).

¹⁸⁸ A similar provision is contained under **article XI (2)(g)** of the **OAU Charter on the Rights and Welfare of the Child**, that the "education of every child shall be directed in such a manner as to the development of respect for the environment and natural resources."

Convention directs States to account for the “dangers and risks of environmental pollution” to ensure full implementation of the right to health for children.

In the Nigerian context, the utility of the above international human rights instruments to the enforcement of environmental rights can only be realised upon ratification and domestication of the said treaty by way of enactment into law by the National Assembly, pursuant to **section 12** of the **Constitution**.¹⁸⁹ It is sad to observe that besides from the African Charter (which is a regional human rights instrument), no other external human rights treaty relevant to environmental protection have been enacted into law.

Given the above, it is clear that the right to environmental protection is recognised under international law. However, there appears to be a disparity in terms of the nature of recognition because while some instruments expressly recognise the right, others see it as an offshoot from other rights. Also, from the communications analysed above, an applicant cannot enforce environmental rights at the international level under international human rights instruments unless the applicant has exhausted local remedies and has satisfied the requirement of proof.

3.4. Applicability of Environmental Rights in Nigeria

The provision of section **6(6)(c)** of the **Constitution** constitutes a clog in the enforcement of the right to environmental protection under **section 20** of the **Constitution**. However, the Nigerian Court in several cases has enforced the directive principles contained under Chapter II of the Constitution, irrespective of its non-justiciability. In the case of *Adamu v. A.G. Borno State*,¹⁹⁰ the Court of Appeal held that the provisions of chapter II are an inbuilt manifesto for political parties and elected officials which programmes and objects they should implement for the people of Nigeria. This means that the citizenry can hold the incumbent government accountable for failing to realise the provisions of Chapter II.

The above interpretation may be far-reaching in terms of the right to environmental protection which is excluded from **Chapter IV** of the **Constitution**. However, the case of *Ransome Kuti v. A.G. Federation*¹⁹¹ gave impetus to the realization of environmental rights in Nigeria. The Supreme Court held that allowing a person to live in an unprotected or downgraded environment could amount to a deprivation of the person’s right to life since the environment can put his life at great risk. From this decision, it became obvious that environmental degradation can ultimately result in the violation of other fundamental rights recognised under

¹⁸⁹ *Supra* note 167.

¹⁹⁰ (1996) 8 NWLR (pt 465) 203.

¹⁹¹ (2001) FWLR (pt 80) 1637.

Chapter IV of the **Constitution**. Hence, the Court in *Gbemre v. Shell*¹⁹² took a firm approach to justify the existence of an environmental right in the light of the right to life and right to dignity provided for under sections **33(1)** and **34(1)** of the **Constitution**.

However, some scholars have questioned the viability of the above approach based on the fact that directive principles contained under **Chapter II** can only be enforced when the National assembly enacts a law that gives effect to it.¹⁹³ This proposition is supported by the Supreme Court's decision in *A.G. Ondo State v. A.G. Federation & Ors.*,¹⁹⁴ where it was held that "courts cannot enforce any of the provisions of Chapter II of the Constitution until the National Assembly has enacted specific laws for their enforcement." It is however submitted that an enactment might not be required to enforce environmental rights where environmental contamination affects a justiciable right, like the right to life, contained under **Chapter IV** of the **Constitution**, in that way rendering a previously non-justiciable provision, justiciable.¹⁹⁵

Furthermore, the enactment of the **African Charter** by the National Assembly has reinforced the applicability of the right to environmental protection in Nigeria. **Section 1** of the enacted Charter shows a clear intention by the government for the Charter to have binding force on every territory and person throughout the federation. It provides that, "As from the commencement of this Act, the provisions of the African Charter on Human and Peoples' Rights which are set out in the schedule to this Act shall, subject as hereunder provided, have force of law in Nigeria and shall be given full recognition and effect and be applied by all authorities and persons exercising legislative, executive or judicial powers in Nigeria."¹⁹⁶ The relevant provision of **section 24** of the **Charter** has already been considered under the regional framework discussed above.

That provision was applied in *Gbemre v. Shell*,¹⁹⁷ where the applicant sought *inter alia* "a declaration that the constitutionally guaranteed fundamental rights to life and dignity of a human person provided in **sections 33(1)** and **34(1)** of the **Constitution of Federal Republic of Nigeria, 1999** and *reinforced by articles 4, 16 and 24 of the African Charter on Human and Peoples' Rights (Ratification and Enforcement) Act, cap A9, voll, Laws of the Federation of Nigeria, 2004 inevitably includes the right to clean poison-free, pollution-free*

¹⁹² *Supra*.

¹⁹³ F. Falana, *Fundamental Rights Enforcement in Nigeria*, 2nd edn. (Lagos: LegalText Publishing Co. Ltd., 2010), p.14.

¹⁹⁴ (2002) 27 WRN 1.

¹⁹⁵ Ekpa, F. Okpanachi, "Enforcing Environmental Rights in Nigeria through the Fundamental Rights (Enforcement Procedure) Rules, 2009". p.105.

¹⁹⁶ *Odafe & Ors v. Attorney-General of the Federation & ors.* (2005) CHR 309, where it was held that "the government of this country has incorporated the African Charter on Human and Peoples' Rights (Ratification and Enforcement) Act, Cap A9, Laws of the Federation of Nigeria, 2004 as part of the law of this country... The African Charter is applicable in this country..." A similar decision was reached in *Abacha v. Fawehinmi (Supra)*.

¹⁹⁷ *Supra*.

and healthy environment.”¹⁹⁸ The court granted the declaration and held that Shell Nigeria and NNPC were to be restrained from further flaring of gas in the applicant’s community and were to take instantaneous measures to end the further flaring of gas in the applicant’s community.

To further lay credence to the applicability of the African Charter to realise environmental protection in Nigeria, Abdulkadir states that: “Arguably, the issue of inconsistency of the Charter with the Constitution does not arise. This is because the provision of **section 6(6)(c)** has only expressly excluded the power of the court with regards to matters listed in the Chapter for Fundamental Objectives and Directives Principles of State Policy in the Constitution. Thus, by deduction, the provision of **section 6(6)(c)** has not referred to any other laws and as such cannot invalidate the justiciable provisions of the Charter.¹⁹⁹ Therefore, the provisions of the Charter having been passed into law by an Act of National Assembly, it confers rights on any person to allege a violation of the Charter before the Nigerian Courts.”²⁰⁰

Worthy of mention is the **Fundamental Rights Enforcement Procedure (FREP) Rules, 2009** which was formulated by the then Chief Justice of Nigeria pursuant to the powers given to him under **section 46(3)** of the **Constitution**.²⁰¹ **Preamble 3(a)** of the 2009 Rules enjoins the court to expansively and purposely interpret and apply Fundamental Rights provisions in the Constitution, and the African Charter on Human and Peoples Right (Ratification and Enforcement) Act with the view to advancing and realizing the rights and freedoms therein contained in them and affording the protections intended by them.²⁰² In *Briggs v. Harry*,²⁰³ **Eko JCA**²⁰⁴ (as he then was) held that the preamble of the FREP Rules enjoins the court to constantly and conscientiously give effect to the overriding principles of the Rules at every stage of human rights action. His Lordship further held that the proactive role of the court advocated by the 2009 Rules enjoins the courts to pursue, where possible, the purpose of advancing but never restricting applicants’ rights to fundamental rights.

The **FREP Rules 2009** proves a viable instrument in realizing the right to environmental protection especially because it recognises public interest environmental action.²⁰⁵ Hence, in

¹⁹⁸ Emphasis added.

¹⁹⁹ This argument is supported by the maxim “*expressio unius, exclusio alterius*” which means that the express stating of a thing is the exclusion of all others.

²⁰⁰ A. B. Abdulkadir, “The Right to a Healthful Environment in Nigeria: A Review of Alternative Pathways to Environmental Justice in Nigeria”, *Afe Babalola University: Journal of Sustainable Development Law and Policy*, Vol.3, Issue 1, 2014, pp.118 – 131 at 126.

²⁰¹ In *Abia State University, Uturu v. Chima Anyaibe* (1996) 1 NWLR (pt.439) 646 at 660 – 1, the Court of appeal held that the Rules have the same force of law as the Constitution itself.

²⁰² Amongst other overriding objectives of the Rules, **Preamble 3(d)** provides that the court in which a fundamental human right action is brought for enforcement is to pursue enhanced access to justice for all classes of litigants. This includes speedy and efficient enforcement of fundamental rights actions as well as hearing priority in deserving cases.

²⁰³ (2016) 9 NWLR 45, 72–73.

²⁰⁴ In the dissenting judgment.

²⁰⁵ **Preamble 3(e)** of the Rules encourages public interest litigation including those brought by NGOs and anyone acting in the public interest. The court is discouraged from striking out or dismissing fundamental rights actions on grounds of *locus standi*.

Centre for Oil Pollution Watch v. Nigerian National Petroleum Corporation,²⁰⁶ the standing of NGOs in environmental actions with public interest dimensions was upheld by the Supreme Court.²⁰⁷ **Eko, J.S.C** found that to broadly determine *locus standi* under environmental rights as human rights, **Article 24** of the **African Charter** should be read together with **Sections 33(1)** and **20** of the **Nigerian Constitution** on the role of the State in preserving the environment for the health and by extension lives of Nigerians.²⁰⁸ His Lordship further held that it is apparent that the right to a healthy environment is a human right in Nigeria having been reproduced under **Articles 24** and **20** of the **African Charter on Peoples and Human Rights (Ratification and Enforcement) Act**.²⁰⁹

From the above, the present state of the law in Nigeria is that there is a right to environmental protection by virtue of the Supreme Courts' decision in *Centre for Oil Pollution Watch v. Nigerian National Petroleum Corporation*. The decision was informed by the provisions of **sections 33(1)** and **20** of the **Constitution**, the African Charter, the liberal provisions of the **FREP Rules 2009**, and the lower courts' decision in *Gbemre v. Shell*. Hence, the non-justiciability of **section 20** of the **Constitution** can no longer be a basis to deny persons their environmental rights.

3.5. Conclusion

The third chapter of this project embarked on a detailed analysis of environmental rights enforcement in Nigeria by considering the national, regional, and international human rights frameworks that apply to Nigeria. The chapter considers the provision of **section 20** of the **Constitution** which recognises environmental protection in Nigeria but which could not be enforced in a court of law because of its non-justiciability. In addition, the chapter discusses the judiciary's approach toward environmental rights in Nigeria in light of specific provisions under **Chapter IV** of the **Constitution** and the **African Charter**. This approach of the Court was aided by the liberal provisions of the **FREP Rules 2009**.

²⁰⁶ *Supra*.

²⁰⁷ A. Babalola, "The Right to a Clean Environment in Nigeria: A Fundamental Right?" 26 *Hastings Env'tl L.J.* 3. Available online at: https://repository.uchastings.edu/hastings_environmental_law_journal/vol26/iss1/2. (Accessed 21 July, 2021).

²⁰⁸ *Supra*. at 597-598.

²⁰⁹ *Ibid*.

CHAPTER FOUR

CASE AND COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF ENVIRONMENTAL RIGHTS ENFORCEMENT IN NIGERIA

4.0. Introduction

The previous chapter of this project examined environmental rights in Nigeria and other jurisdictions (at the international and regional level). That chapter analysed the constitutional provision on environmental protection in Nigeria and the attitude of the Court in recent years towards enforcing the right to environment. However, what is not clear was the attitude of the Court in Nigeria before this recent development. This chapter thus attempts to trace the history of environmental rights enforcement to environmental civil litigation, in order to uncover the defects of that regime so as to determine the usefulness of this present regime. Also, this chapter undertakes a study on the enforcement of environmental rights in India to derive lessons from the judicial attitude in that jurisdiction, as well as identify the distinctions in the approach of the Court in India with that of Nigeria. This chapter further looks at the various institutions and laws involved in upholding the right to environmental protection in Nigeria, identifying their potentials and shortcomings (if any) in achieving the object.

4.1. Selected Cases on Environmental Rights in Nigeria

Prior to the establishment of environmental rights in Nigeria by virtue of the Court's decision in *Jonah Gbemre v. Shell*,²¹⁰ affected parties of environmental pollution sought remedy under the environmental civil litigation. This domain was governed by the general principles of torts law²¹¹, and the law of evidence, so that when a litigant failed to satisfy the requirements of proving damages and establishing the causal connection between the environmental pollution and the damage claimed, which required an expert witness, the Court was likely to hold against him. The cases to be examined under this section are divided into two: The first three cases were decided before the environmental rights regime, while the subsequent two cases entrenched the right to environmental protection in Nigeria. The judicial attitude of the Courts is of utmost importance in this analysis. Unlike the Courts in the first two cases, there was a change in the attitude of the Court in *Shell v. Farah*,²¹² where compensation was not only awarded for the injury suffered as a result of damage caused to the environment, but also for the rehabilitation of the environment.

²¹⁰ (2005) AHRLR 151.

²¹¹ Claims were in most cases founded on the tort of negligence.

²¹² (1995) 3 NWLR.

4.1.1. *Shell v. Tiebo VII*²¹³

The case was brought by the chiefs of the Perembiri community in their personal capacity and on behalf of the village community for negligence following a crude oil spill resulting from facilities belonging to Shell. The oil spill caused damage to farmland, fishing grounds, water sources and religious shrines, and disrupted the livelihood of the community, of which a significant proportion are children. Moreover, the plaintiffs claimed that, apart from polluting their source of drinking water, the spill killed fish in the swamps and 40 ponds belonging to the community, destroyed their economic trees (such as raffia palms), caused water-borne diseases for members of the community who drank the contaminated water, and generally paralyzed the subsistence and economic life of members of the community who were predominantly fishermen.²¹⁴

The defendant, in its defence, though not denying the occurrence of the pollution and its possible impact on the environment, denied the extent of the pollution and the degree of damage suffered. Specifically, it claimed that the pollution affected only a smaller area (2.3 hectares) of the plaintiffs' swamp and fish flats, and offered a sum of 5,500 naira as 'fair and adequate compensation, which the plaintiffs rejected. At the trial court, the plaintiffs were awarded general damages of 5,000,000.00 naira, as well as a one million naira intended to cover their legal costs. The trial court held that "*I have found in this case and as was admitted by the defendant, that crude oil applied or gushed or escaped from their Diebu Creek flow-station, Well 12T, and flowed from the defendant's acquired land, onto the lands, waters, creeks and ponds of the plaintiffs and consequently the plaintiffs suffered general damages for the pollution...*"²¹⁵ Also, due to the plaintiff's inability to prove their entitlement to special damages for damage to raffia palms and loss of drinking water, the court concluded that this unsuccessful claim for special damages should instead be awarded in the form of general damages of 400,000.00 naira and 600,000.00 naira (respectively).

The defendants were aggrieved with the quantum of damages awarded and appealed to the Court of Appeal, which dismissed their action. Further appeal to the Supreme Court was dismissed. The Court per **Oguntade JSC** held that it would only interfere with the amount of an award of damages if the award were "manifestly too high" or "manifestly too little", or if the judge had relied on an incorrect principle of damages in making the award.²¹⁶ The Court

²¹³ (2005) 9 NWLR (Pt.931) 439.

²¹⁴ The plaintiffs claimed to have 'suffered environmentally, socially, economically and medically'. Culled from *Ibid*.

²¹⁵ *Ibid*.

²¹⁶ Relying on the decision of **ESO JSC** in *West African Shipping Agency v. Kalla* (1978) 3 SC 21 at 32, which was a restatement of the principle established in *Dumez (Nig.) Ltd. v. Ogboli* (1972) 1 All NLR 241, per **Lewis JSC**.

also pointed out that the trial Court was wrong in awarding general damages for damage to raffia palms and loss of drinking water, which are claims under special damages requiring specific proof. In the absence of such proof, the Supreme Court set it aside and upheld only the general damages of 5million naira.

From this decision, it is notable to observe that no order was made by the Court for the remediation of damage done to the physical environment – specifically on land resources and the water systems that serve as sources of potable water supply to the plaintiffs.²¹⁷

4.1.2. *Shell v. Isaiah*²¹⁸

This case was also instituted based on the tort of negligence. In July 1988, an old tree fell on the defendant's oil pipeline and indented it. The indentation hindered the free flow of crude oil through the said pipelines which ran across the plaintiff's swampland and surrounding farmlands. The defendant engaged the services of a contractor to repair the dented pipeline. In the cause of the repairs, the defendant neglected to construct an oil trap²¹⁹ so that crude oil freely spilled onto the plaintiff's swampland and polluted the surrounding farmlands, streams and fishponds. In consequence, all the uses to which they put the land were destroyed. The damage affected both surface rights and the environment.

The plaintiff claimed against the defendant at the High Court sitting at Isiokpo, Rivers State the sum of 22 million naira for damages resulting from the defendant's negligent activities. In its defence, the defendant oil company contended that there was no oil spillage, but a 'minor splash of oil'. The trial court and the Court of Appeal honoured the claim of damages sought by the plaintiffs, and found that there was 'massive oil spillage', causing extensive damage to 'economic crops, economic trees...water resources and hunting amenities'.²²⁰

On appeal to the Supreme Court, the decisions of the lower courts were reversed on the basis of lack of jurisdiction of the State High Court to entertain claims concerning mines and minerals including oil fields²²¹ by virtue of the **Federal High Court (Amendment) Act**²²² and **section 230(1)(o) of the Constitution (Suspension and Modification)**²²³. Those provisions bring the matter within the exclusive jurisdiction of the Federal High Court. The Supreme Court

²¹⁷ Ebeku, S. A. Kaniye, "Judicial Attitudes to Redress for Oil-Related Environmental Damage in Nigeria." *Review of European Community and International Environmental Law* 12 (2003): 199-208. Available online at <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/epdf/10.1111/1467-9388.00360> (accessed 6 August, 2021).

²¹⁸ (2001) 11 N.W.L.R. (Part 723) 168.

²¹⁹ A device constructed in the soil for the purpose of trapping oil in the course of such repairs.

²²⁰ *Supra* note 217.

²²¹ The Supreme Court referred to the **Petroleum Act** 1960 and the **Oil Pipelines Act** 1956 and found that the most important aspect of oil mining operation is the construction of oil pipeline.

²²² Decree No. 60 of 1991.

²²³ Decree No. 107 of 1993.

refused to follow the argument of the plaintiff's counsel that the amendment provision which affected the jurisdiction of the State High Court came into force after the cause of action arose in Court. The Supreme Court per **Mohammed JSC** held that, while it was correct that the cause of action arose before the promulgation of the law; the trial was in progress when the law was made and as such the law could not operative retroactively to affect the outcome of the case. From that moment when the law was signed, the jurisdiction of the trial court was ousted. Similarly, **Belgore JSC** held that, once the jurisdiction of a court is ousted, the court assuming jurisdiction does so as an exercise either in moot or as an academic exercise but certainly in futility.²²⁴

From this case, the trial court and Court of Appeal awarded only monetary compensation to the plaintiffs, with no consequential remedial measures for rehabilitation of the physical environment (land and water resources). The subsequent decision of the Supreme Court which reversed those of the lower courts is a clear indication of how the issue of jurisdiction can act as an impediment to environmental justice.²²⁵

4.1.3. *Shell v. Farah*²²⁶

Five families in the K-Dere community in Rivers State sued Shell for damages on grounds of negligence occasioned by the defendant's oil production activities. As recounted by the Court of Appeal, the case concerned an oil blowout that occurred in July 1970 from an oil well known as Bomu well-11, which was owned and operated by Shell. The blow-out²²⁷ lasted for several weeks before it was brought under control, during which time crude hydrocarbon, sulphur and effluent toxic substances were violently emitted in dense fountains. The emissions allegedly formed a thick layer over the surface of the plaintiffs' adjoining land, destroying farmlands, crops and economic trees, and natural vegetation of the impacted areas, with the resultant destruction of an impacted area of about 607 hectares. Before the incident, the plaintiffs used the land for farming and hunting. Apart from asking for compensation, the plaintiffs' specifically asked for the rehabilitation of their lands.

Interestingly, the defendant accepted responsibility and paid compensation to the plaintiffs for the crops and economic trees destroyed at the time of the incident,²²⁸ but paid no compensation for the damages to the plaintiffs' land, which they 'took over'. However, the defendant did promise to rehabilitate the affected lands. Fourteen years after the incident, the defendant had

²²⁴ *Supra* note 217.

²²⁵ S.A. Fagbemi, A.R. Akpanke, "Environmental Litigation in Nigeria: the Role of the Judiciary." *Nnamdi Azikiwe University Journal of International Law and Jurisprudence*. Vol. 10 No. 2 (2019).

²²⁶ (1995) 3 NWLR.

²²⁷ Regarded in oil industry circles as an operational accident.

²²⁸ 22,000 pounds in compensation for damaged crops, trees and other objects and another 1,000 pounds for damage to the land.

still not fulfilled its promise to rehabilitate the land, and the plaintiffs sued. They argued before the trial court that the land had not been rehabilitated, and the defendants had failed to comply with its duty to pay fair compensation for the damages suffered.

At the trial court, the Court was confronted with two main issues: (1) whether the plaintiffs had been paid 'adequate compensation; and (2) whether the land had been rehabilitated. Both parties in the suit brought expert witnesses to support their case. The expert witness of the plaintiff, who had studied the post-incident impact on the plaintiffs' lands, stated that the soil samples studied were acidic and poor in total nitrogen as a result of the oil spillage. Accordingly, he observed that a large portion of the affected land could not support plant growth. He concluded that the area cannot be deemed to have been rehabilitated to its pre-impact conditions and cannot be so unless certain further actions are taken.²²⁹ On the other hand, the expert witness of the defendant argued that land had been rehabilitated. He stated that his study²³⁰ showed that in the badly affected area where crop performance was poor, the surface soil had been removed as a result of erosion occasioned by poor management. In his opinion, "soils of the area are inherently poor in fertility and the badly affected area by virtue of its depressional position had all that physical impediment."²³¹ In conclusion, he stated that "the poor performance of the crops in this area was not due to the pressure of crude oil."²³²

In a bid to resolve the conflicting expert evidence adduced on behalf of both parties, the trial Judge appointed two independent experts, one each nominated by the plaintiffs and the defendant. Their joint report to the court supported the findings of the plaintiffs' expert witness.²³³ Based on this, the trial Judge accepted the evidence of the plaintiff's expert witness and rejected that of the defendant, which he adjudged as not representing the true position of things. The Court concluded that the land needed rehabilitation.²³⁴ The decision of the trial judge was upheld by the Court of Appeal. The latter court decided that "The damage the respondents (plaintiffs) suffered went beyond a mere damage to crops and economic trees, for according to the experts called on both sides the respondents'(plaintiffs') arable land was heavily polluted and rendered unproductive for many years."²³⁵ Accordingly, the Court of Appeal awarded the plaintiffs 4.6 million Naira as compensation and upheld the order for the rehabilitation of damaged land.

²²⁹ Details on the expert evidence is found in *Supra* note 225, at 181-182.

²³⁰ The study was carried out by a team of experts, but only one gave evidence on behalf of the others in court.

²³¹ *Supra* note 225, at 180-182.

²³² *Ibid.*

²³³ *Supra* note 225, at 182-183.

²³⁴ *Ibid.* at 184.

²³⁵ *Ibid.* at 176.

Flowing from the above, the pleadings and decision in this case are significant to environmental justice because it is the first case where a plaintiff sought both compensation and remediation to damaged land, which was given attendance to by the Court. In addition, the decision was accompanied by more relaxed rules of evidence especially with the appointment of independent expert witnesses by the trial Judge to resolve the conflict of the expert testimony given for both sides.²³⁶ Also, Frynas noted that the case is “an important judicial precedent regarding the quantum of compensation for damage”.²³⁷ Overall, this case paved the way for change by rendering it easier to sue oil companies for environmental damage.

4.1.4. *Jonah Gbemre v. Shell Petroleum Development Company of Nigeria*²³⁸

Mr. Gbemre in a representative capacity for himself and every member of the Iwehereken community in Delta State, Nigeria filed the suit against Shell Nigeria, Nigerian National Petroleum Corporation (NNPC) and the Attorney General of the Federation to end gas flaring in the community. The plaintiff argued that gas flaring violated their right to enjoy a healthy environment as provided by **Article 24** of the **African Charter** and the constitutional guarantee of the right to life and dignity of persons provided for in **sections 33** and **34** of the **1999 Constitution**.

The High Court per **Judge Nwokorie** declared that the actions of the 1st and 2nd Respondents in continuing to flare gas in the course of their oil exploration and production activities in the applicant’s community is a violation of their fundamental right to life (including healthy environment) and dignity of human persons guaranteed by the Constitution and the African Charter. The Court further declared that the 1st and 2nd Respondents; Shell Nigeria and NNPC were to be restrained from further flaring of gas in the applicant’s community and were to take immediate steps to stop the further flaring of gas in the applicant’s community.

The Court made the following declaratory orders, *inter alia*:

- That the constitutionally guaranteed fundamental rights to life and dignity of human persons provided by **Sections 33(1)** and **34(1)** of the **Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria, 1999** and reinforced by **Article 4, 16** and **24** of the **African Charter on Human Procedure Rules (Procedure and Enforcement) Act Cap A9 Vol.1 Laws of the Federation of Nigeria, 2004** inevitably includes the right to clean poison-free, pollution-free and healthy environment.

²³⁶ *Supra* note 217.

²³⁷ *Ibid.*

²³⁸ (2005) AHRLR 151.

- That the actions of the 1st and 2nd Respondent in continuing to flare gas in the course of their oil exploration and production activities in the Applicant’s community is a violation of their fundamental right to life (including healthy environment) and dignity of human persons guaranteed by the Constitution and the African Charter.
- That the provisions of **Section 3(2)(a) and (b) of the Associated Gas Reinjection Act, Cap A25 Vol. 1, Laws of the Federation of Nigeria 2004 and Section 1 of the Associated Gas Reinjection (continued flaring of gas) Regulations Section 1.43** of 1984 under which the continued flaring of gas in Nigeria may be permitted are inconsistent with the Applicant’s Right to life and/or dignity of the human person enshrined in the constitution and the African Charter and are therefore unconstitutional, null and void by virtue of **Section 1(3) of the Nigerian Constitution.**

The decision is a watershed for environmental rights enforcement in Nigeria. The first of its kind, marking the beginning of an end to environmental pollution especially gas flaring of oil companies in Nigeria through the rights-based approach.²³⁹ However, because the decision was made by the High Court, it is by no means the “law” since it can still be overturned on appeal.²⁴⁰ Hence, it was much needed for the Supreme Court to make a similar pronouncement so that the right to environmental protection can be fully realised for all people.

4.1.4. *Centre for Oil Pollution Watch v. Nigerian National Petroleum Corporation*²⁴¹

This case was an opportunity for the Supreme Court to assert its position on whether a right to a clean and healthy environment exists in Nigeria. The Court extended the frontiers of *locus standi* for environmental matters. The brief facts of this case were that the appellant (a Non-Governmental Organization), commenced an action at the Federal High Court, Lagos, against the defendant (NNPC) over an alleged oil spillage in Acha Community of Isukwuato Local Government Area of Abia State. The plaintiff claimed that the oil spillage had affected the Community and its environment, making life miserable for the inhabitants. The plaintiff therefore claimed reinstatement, restoration and remediation of the impaired and contaminated environment; potable water supply as a substitute for the contaminated streams; and provision of medical facilities for the evaluation and treatment of affected victims of the oil spillage.

²³⁹ It is the first judicial authority to declare that gas flaring is illegal, unconstitutional, a breach of the fundamental human right to life and it should cease. Culled from O. Adejowo-Osho, *Op. cit.* 18.

²⁴⁰ This is because Nigeria operates the principle of *Stare decisis*, (derived from the maxim “*stare decisis et non queita movere*” - let it stand, what has been decided should not move) which means that the decisions of the higher courts in the hierarchy of courts are binding on the lower courts. This is otherwise known as ‘Judicial Precedent’.

²⁴¹ (2019) 5 NWLR (Pt. 1666) 518.

In its defence, the defendant challenged the *locus standi*²⁴² of the plaintiff to commence the action and prayed the court to strike out the suit. The trial court upheld the contention and struck out the suit. On appeal, the Court of Appeal dismissed the appeal filed by the appellant and held that the appellant lacked sufficient interest and that the members of the community were better placed and armed with standing for the case. Still aggrieved, the plaintiff approached the Supreme Court.

The Supreme Court had to invite some *amicus curiae*²⁴³ to assist in the determination of the issue of whether the plaintiff has a right to institute the action. The *amicus curiae* canvassed for the liberalization of the concept of standing, by considering environmental rights as human rights. He argued that **section 33** of the Nigerian **Constitution** provides for the right to life and any act or omission that threatens the health of the people of the community also threatens their lives and is in breach of the guaranteed right to life provided by the Constitution.²⁴⁴ **Eko JSC** agreed with the *amicus curiae* and found that to broadly determine *locus standi* under environmental rights as human rights, **Article 24** of the **African Charter** should be read together with **sections 33(1)** and **20** of the Nigerian **Constitution** on the role of the State in preserving the environment for the health and by extension lives of Nigerians.²⁴⁵

Ultimately, **Eko JSC** found that it is apparent that the right to a healthy environment is a human right in Nigeria.²⁴⁶ His Lordship reproduced **Articles 24**²⁴⁷ and **20**²⁴⁸ of the **African Charter** and held that as long as Nigeria remains a signatory to the African Charter, and other global as well, the Nigerian Courts would protect and vindicate human rights entrenched therein.²⁴⁹ Similarly, **Kekere-Ekun JSC** made the finding that: **Sections 33** and **20** of the Nigerian **Constitution**; **Article 24** of the **African Charter**; and **Section 17(4)** of the **Oil Pipelines Act** show that the Constitution, the legislature and the African Charter on Human and Peoples' Rights, to which Nigeria is a signatory, recognise the fundamental rights of the citizenry to a clean and healthy environment to sustain life.²⁵⁰

4.2. Comparative Analysis of Environmental Rights in India

²⁴² That is, right to sue.

²⁴³ Friends of the Court.

²⁴⁴ *Supra* note 241. at 559–560 and 597–598.

²⁴⁵ *Ibid.* at 597-598.

²⁴⁶ *Ibid.*

²⁴⁷ All peoples shall have the right to a general satisfactory environment favourable to their development.

²⁴⁸ All peoples shall have right to existence. They shall have the unquestionable and inalienable right to self-determination. They shall freely determine their political status and shall pursue their economic and social development according to the policy they have freely chosen.

²⁴⁹ *Supra* note 241. at 598.

²⁵⁰ *Ibid.* at 587.

Nigeria and India share a lot in common from a historical²⁵¹, constitutional vis-a-vis environmental protection²⁵² and economic development perspective²⁵³. However, there are variations in the attitude of the Courts in both Nations towards the realization of environmental rights. Unlike Nigeria,²⁵⁴ the Indian Courts have since the early 1990s upheld the right to environmental protection by construing **Articles 48A**²⁵⁵ and **51A**²⁵⁶ of the Indian Constitution (on environmental protection) in the light of the right to life provision under **Article 21** of the Constitution.²⁵⁷ Hence, in the case of *Subhash Kumar v. State of Bihar*,²⁵⁸ the Court observed that “right to life guaranteed by **Article 21** includes the right of enjoyment of pollution-free water and air for full enjoyment of life” and in *Mathur v. Union of India*,²⁵⁹ the Supreme Court used the right to life as a basis for emphasizing the need to take drastic steps to combat air and water pollution.²⁶⁰

It could be argued that the reason for the delay in giving effect to environmental rights in Nigeria was due to the role of the government in oil exploration activities.²⁶¹ Accordingly, it became the habit of the Courts in a plethora of cases where there is a conflict between State economic interests and the public interest (that is, environmental protection) to hold against the latter²⁶² since a decision against a multinational oil corporation would automatically be a decision against the government.²⁶³ In contrast, the Indian government’s interest is limited only to its regulatory responsibility.²⁶⁴

Consequently, in the case of *Rural Litigation and Entitlement Kendra v. Union of India*,²⁶⁵ when the Supreme Court was called upon to resolve the conflict between the need for economic benefits on the one hand, and environmental protection on the other, the Court held in favour

²⁵¹ Both being British colonies before independence.

²⁵² Both have the relevant provisions of environmental protection contained in the chapters on Fundamental Objectives and Directive Principle of State Policy under their respective Constitutions, which are generally not enforceable against the State.

²⁵³ Though India is not an oil producing nation, its mining industry engage in mining activities that have some environmental consequences similar to oil extraction.

²⁵⁴ It was not until 2003, following the decision in *Gbemre v. Shell*, that the judicial attitude changed towards the enforcement of environmental rights.

²⁵⁵ Which provides that, the state shall endeavour to protect the environment and to safeguard the forest and wildlife.

²⁵⁶ It provides that, it will be the duty of every citizen to protect and improve the natural environment of the country and to have compassion for living creatures.

²⁵⁷ In *Tarun Bharat Sangh, Alwar v. Union of India*, 1992 Supp (2) SCC 448, the Court held that issues of environment must and shall receive the highest attention from this Court.

²⁵⁸ AIR 1991 SC 420.

²⁵⁹ (1996) 1 SCC 119.

²⁶⁰ T. A. Ruhs, “The Judicial Recognition and Enforcement of the Right to Environment: Differing Perspectives from Nigeria and India.” *National University of Juridical Sciences Law Review*, Vol. 3, p. 423, 2010. Available online at https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=1796824 (assessed 8 August, 2021).

²⁶¹ The federal government through the national oil company (NNPC) is the major shareholder in joint-venture agreements with foreign oil-multinationals that operate the oil industry.

²⁶² *Allan Irou v. Shell BP* Suit No. W/89/91 Warri HC/26/11/73 (Unreported).

²⁶³ Again, it can further be argued that the absence of an independent judiciary (especially under the military regime) was a major contributor to the decisions of the Court.

²⁶⁴ It should not be taken to mean that the attitude of the Court in India would have been any different if the government were stakeholders in the mining activities. This point is only made to emphasize that, while the Nigerian Courts were under pressure to dance to the tune of the government, the Indian Courts did not have similar experience.

²⁶⁵ AIR 1985 SC 652.

of the latter.²⁶⁶ In this case, lessees of mines challenged the decision of the *Bandyopadhyay* Committee in rejecting their scheme for limestone quarrying. The Court held that the environmental considerations outweighed the economic benefits of the project and thus approved the decision of the *Bandyopadhyay* Committee.

Additionally, the Court of India in the case of *Kinkri Devi and Another v. State of Himachal Pradesh and Others*²⁶⁷ recognised the duties of the State towards environmental protection.²⁶⁸ The Court held that operations from the mines which were alleged by the petitioner to impose danger to the adjoining land, water resources and inhabitants of the area, should stop pending the government's proper determination of the balance between development and environment from mining operations and submission of the report to the Court.²⁶⁹ The Court reasoned that **Articles 48A**²⁷⁰ of the Indian Constitution placed a constitutional duty on the State to protect and improve the environment and that it (the Court) was left with no alternative but to intervene effectively by issuing appropriate orders in furtherance of this duty.

Another comparison lies within the ambit of the Constitution of both Countries. Unlike **section 20** of the Nigerian Constitution, the Indian constitution went a step further under **Article 51A(g)** to provide for the fundamental duty of every citizen in the country to protect and improve the natural environment including forests, lakes, rivers, all other water resources and wildlife. This provision was upheld by the Court in the celebrated case of *M.C. Mehta v. Union of India*,²⁷¹ which was a public interest litigation brought by the petitioner against the government administrators as well as the tanneries whose effluents polluted the River Ganga. The Court held that it was the fundamental duty of every citizen to protect and improve the natural environment just as it was a duty of the State to protect and improve the quality of the environment. Accordingly, the Court decided that a tannery that cannot set up a primary treatment plant cannot be permitted to continue to be in existence particularly as the possible impacts of continued effluent discharge into the River Ganga would outweigh the inconveniences caused to the management and labour employed by it on account of the closure of the tanneries.

The provision and decision of the Court examined above show that the question of *locus standi* does not pose any problem in the enforcement of the right to environmental protection in the

²⁶⁶ *Supra* note 260.

²⁶⁷ AIR 1988 HP 4.

²⁶⁸ A feat which was only achieved recently by the Nigerian Supreme Court in *Centre for Oil Pollution Watch v. NNPC*, where **Eko JSC** held that the right to life provision (**section 33**) and **section 20** of the **Constitution** recognises the role of the State in preserving the environment for the health and by extension lives of Nigerians.

²⁶⁹ The Court also held that no lease for mining of limestone was to be granted or renewed nor temporary permits issued till the report of the committee is received.

²⁷⁰ It states that, the State shall endeavour to protect and improve the environment and to safeguard the forests and wild life of the country.

²⁷¹ (1996) 4 SCC 351.

Indian jurisdiction since every member of the society has a responsibility and duty towards the safeguarding of the environment. In contrast, it was not until recently, following the Supreme Court's decision in *Centre for Oil Pollution Watch v. NNPC*,²⁷² that the Supreme Court of Nigeria liberalized the concept of *locus standi* to enable the enforcement of environmental rights.

Flowing from the above, the Indian Courts have an established jurisprudence for the enforcement of environmental rights by not only recognizing the existence of the right but also acknowledging the duties of the State and citizens towards environmental protection. While it is not in doubt that the Courts in India have been aided by their constitutional provision that places a duty on the Citizens to safeguard the environment, the Nigerian Courts can learn from their attitude in giving priority to environmental protection over economic benefits. It is worth acknowledging the improvement in the attitude of the Nigerian Courts towards the enforcement of environmental rights. However, like India, more Supreme Courts' decisions on the enforcement of environmental rights are required to nullify any doubt as to the existence of the right in Nigeria.

4.3. Upholding Environmental Rights in Nigeria

While there is no denying the existence of the right to environmental protection in Nigeria, a lot still has to be done for the right to be fully realised in the Country. The mere fact there are legislations²⁷³ or judicial decisions giving effect to the right to environmental protection does not make it effective. Without proper enforcement mechanisms, judicial decisions will be a mere exercise in futility.²⁷⁴ In Nigeria, the lack of proper enforcement of judicial decisions has plagued the realization of the right to environmental protection. For instance, in the aftermath of *Gbemre v. Shell*,²⁷⁵ the defendant disregarded the long list of declaratory orders pronounced by the Court, without any resultant consequence.²⁷⁶ Government influence was a major contributor to the lack of enforcement of the decision as is evident from the fact that the Judge had been removed from the case having been transferred to another court in Katsina and the court registry could not locate the case file.²⁷⁷

²⁷² *Supra*.

²⁷³ The simple reason is that the law is not a paper tiger.

²⁷⁴ Hence the maxim, *lex non cogit ad impossibilia* (The law does not command the doing of impossibilities).

²⁷⁵ The decision of the Court in this case has not been effective in ending industrial pollution by oil companies. For instance, in 2004 and 2008, two separate oil spills from a Shell facility occurred polluting several fishing communities in the Niger Delta, amongst which includes - Ikot Ada Udo in Akwa Ibom state; Goi in Rivers state; and Oruma in Bayelsa state.

²⁷⁶ Shell hid under the cloak of appeal to evade court order and thus refused to comply with the court Order to end gas flaring in Iwherekan. Culled from G. U. Ojo, PhD, N. Tokunbor, "Access to Environmental Justice in Nigeria: The Case for a Global Environmental Court of Justice", *Friends of the Earth International*, October 2016, available online at <https://www.foei.org/wp-content/uploads/2016/10/Environmental-Justice-Nigeria-Shell-English.pdf> (accessed 8 August, 2021).

²⁷⁷ *Ibid*.

Moreover, it was discovered at the Court of Appeal hearing that the matter had been incorrectly adjourned by court officials without notice to the applicant or his lawyers. Although the chief Judge stated that the reason for this would be investigated and the individual involved would be penalized, no additional information has been made public.²⁷⁸ Reacting to the odd events, Roderick observes as follows: “*The fact that the Judge has been removed from the case transferred to the north of the country, and there have been problems with the court file for a second time, suggests a degree of interference in the judicial system which is unacceptable in a purported democracy acting under the rule of law.*”²⁷⁹

The Court plays a crucial role in the realization of environmental rights in Nigeria. Hence, the barriers to the enforcement of judicial decisions on environmental protection must be lifted. On this premise, it is recommended that the Court should explore the growing jurisprudence on the right to environment internationally and use this as one of the bases for its judgement. For instance, the Indian Courts’ decisions on environmental protection contain rich references to the international precepts upon which the right to a healthy environment are founded and refer to the growing jurisprudence on these issues.²⁸⁰ The essence of this is that, when international precepts are properly applied to judicial pronouncements, rather than mere declarative orders,²⁸¹ it makes enforcements more practicable and the government of the day would be bound to abide and respect them in view of the *pacta sunt servanda* principle.²⁸² In addition, for Nigeria to truly move forward and become a real democratic society where rights are guaranteed without hitches, there must be an independent judiciary. It is hoped that subsequent decisions on environmental pollution would follow the same line of thinking as the Supreme Court in *Centre for Oil Pollution Watch* case,²⁸³ where the Justices manifested great respect for the rule of law and fundamental human rights, by reinforcing Nigeria’s obligation to respect international human rights standards contained in treaties to which Nigeria is a party.

Additionally, the regulatory framework on environmental protection helps to consolidate the right to environmental protection. One such regulation is the **NESREA Act, 2007** which is the principal legislation for environmental protection in Nigeria. The Act establishes the Agency for environmental standards, regulations, rules, laws, policies and guidelines.²⁸⁴ The Agency

²⁷⁸ *Supra* note 260.

²⁷⁹ Friends of the Earth International Press Briefing, *Shell fails to obey gas flaring court order*, May 2, 2007. Available online at http://www.foe.co.uk/resource/press_releases/shell_fails_to_obey_gas_fl_02052007.html (accessed 8 August, 2021).

²⁸⁰ *Supra* note 260.

²⁸¹ As was the case in *Gbemre v. Shell (Supra)*.

²⁸² The Indian courts are guided by the **Bangalore Principle** which upholds the utilization of the provisions contained in international human rights instrument which a country has ratified but not domesticated as tool of construction to remove ambiguities and uncertainties in domestic laws. It was adopted at the end of a Judicial Colloquium on the Domestic Application of International Human Rights Instruments held in Bangalore, India 1998.

²⁸³ *Supra* note 241.

²⁸⁴ **Section 1** of the **NESREA Act**.

has responsibility for the protection and development of the environment, biodiversity conservation and sustainable development of Nigeria's natural resources.²⁸⁵ The Act also gives the Agency powers to make regulations setting specifications and standards concerning the air quality and atmospheric protection²⁸⁶ to protect and enhance the quality of Nigeria's air resources, so as to promote public health, *inter alia*.²⁸⁷

Another relevant legislation is the **EIA Act**, 1992 which was established to set out the general principles, procedures, and methods to enable the prior consideration of environmental impact assessment on certain public or private projects.²⁸⁸ The Act ensures that written applications are submitted to the Agency before embarking on projects for their environmental assessment to determine approval.²⁸⁹ Despite the utility of this Act, there has been a high level of non-compliance with its provisions by multinational oil companies, with no sanction imposed by the Agency on the violators.²⁹⁰

Worthy of mention is the **National Human Rights Commission** (NHRC) of Nigeria,²⁹¹ established for the protection of human rights, dignity, and freedoms guaranteed by the Constitution, the African Charter on Human and Peoples' Rights, the U.N. Charter and the UDHR and other International Treaties on human rights to which Nigeria is a signatory. Amongst its many functions, the relevant ones to environmental justice include: To monitor and investigate all alleged cases of human rights violation in Nigeria and make appropriate recommendations to the President for the prosecution and such other actions as it may deem expedient in each circumstance; Assist victims of human rights violation and seek appropriate redress and remedies on their behalf; Organize local and international seminars, workshops and conferences on human rights issues for public enlightenment; Liaise and co-operate with local and international organizations on human rights with the purpose of advancing the promotion and protection of human rights.²⁹² As an alternative to the Court, victims of environmental pollution may petition the Commission to enforce their environmental rights.

²⁸⁵ **Section 2**, *Ibid.*

²⁸⁶ The Act confers wide regulatory powers on the Agency, leaving the Agency itself to work out the specific details such as rules and standards to be observed in environmental use. By this, the Agency may adopt best international practices and standards in its regulation that are well suited to ensure a sustainable use of the environment.

²⁸⁷ **Section 20** of the **NESREA Act**.

²⁸⁸ **Section 2(1)** of the **EIA Act**.

²⁸⁹ **Section 2(4)** of the **EIA Act**.

²⁹⁰ Even though **section 20** of the **EIA Act** contains legal liability for the contravention of any of its provisions.

²⁹¹ Established by the **National Human Rights Commission Act** No. 22 of 1995 (as amended by NHRC (Amendment) Act 2010) in line with Resolution 48/134 of the United Nations General Assembly which enjoins all member States to establish independent National Institutions for the promotion, protection, and enforcement of Human Rights. Culled from National Human Rights commission website. Available at <https://www.nigeriarights.gov.ng/index.php> (accessed 8 August 2021).

²⁹² **Section 5** of the **NHRC Act**.

In addition, the citizens of Nigeria have a personal responsibility towards the environment to safeguard and maintain it,²⁹³ even though no such duty is provided for under the Constitution. However, it is argued that this duty can be read into **section 24(d)** of the **Constitution** which states that it shall be the duty of every citizen to – make positive and useful contributions to the advancement, progress and well-being of the community where he resides.²⁹⁴ The necessity of this duty is that human beings are naturally selfish and would only care about environmental pollution when it affects their business venture or their general livelihood. Hence, there is a need for the relevant government agencies to impose a duty of safeguarding and protecting the environment on their citizenry. Such agencies include NESREA, NOSDRA,²⁹⁵ National Agency for Food and Drug Administration and Control (NAFDAC),²⁹⁶ the Nigerian Police,²⁹⁷ State and local government environmental protection agencies,²⁹⁸ amongst others.

From the foregoing, while it is beyond any shadow of a doubt as to the existence of environmental right in Nigeria, the said right would be futile unless the Courts, citizens and the relevant agencies carry out their various obligations towards environmental protection. In the same vein, the Constitution by virtue of **section 13** imposes an obligation on the executive and the legislative arm of government to conform to, observe and apply the provisions of **chapter II** which includes **section 20** (on environmental protection).²⁹⁹ In sum, all hands must be on deck for environmental rights to be fully realised for all people.

4.4. Conclusion

This chapter embarked on a case analysis on the enforcement of environmental rights in Nigeria in a bid to show and contrast the differing attitudes of the Courts under the environmental civil litigation regime, and the environmental rights regime. While there are few case laws in the latter, it is hoped that the trend of enforcing environmental rights would continue. In addition, a comparative analysis on environmental rights enforcement in India was examined, and lessons were deduced from that jurisdiction, especially the willingness of the Court to protect the environment even though at the expense of economic benefit. The chapter also considered

²⁹³ This is because human beings by deforestation, overgrazing during cattle rearing, burning of fusel fuel, and disposing of wastes onto land and water, have made dramatic contributions to environmental degradation in Nigeria.

²⁹⁴ By reducing gas emissions, using renewable sources of energy, refraining from disposing sewage or other domestic wastes onto the water or land, reduction in the use of plastics, amongst others, the duty would be successfully discharged.

²⁹⁵ The Federal Government established this agency as an institutional framework to implement the National oil spill contingency plan which is a manual for checking oil spill through, containment, recovery and remediation. Culled from H. Ijaiya, O. T. Joseph, "Rethinking Environmental Law Enforcement in Nigeria", *Beijing Law Review*, 2014, 5, 306-321. Available online at <http://dx.doi.org/10.4236/blr.2014.54029> (accessed 10 August, 2021).

²⁹⁶ An Agency under the Federal Ministry of Health. It issues permits to industries for importation of foods, cosmetic and chemicals.

²⁹⁷ **Section 10** of the NESREA gives them powers to conduct a warrantless search on any building, land, carrier, aircraft or any other thing whatsoever which they have reasons to believe is related to the commission of a crime under the Act.

²⁹⁸ The Lagos State Waste Management Authority (LAWMA) and Lagos State Environmental Protection Agency (LASEPA), are the notable environmental protection Agencies in the State, established under **section 4(2)** of the **Lagos State Environmental Management and Protection Law (LSEMPL)**, 2017.

²⁹⁹ As earlier mentioned under chapter three of this project, the provision on non-justiciability under **section 6(6)(c)** of the **Constitution** affects only the judiciary, with the exclusion of the executive and legislature.

the various factors that have prevented the Court from enforcing environmental rights and proffered a way forward by advocating that the Court should rely on international human rights principles, while also recognizing the role of other stakeholders in protecting the environment.

CHAPTER FIVE

RECOMMENDATIONS AND CONCLUSION

5.0. General Overview and Summary

This project embarked on a journey to justify the viability of the rights-based approach in securing environmental justice and sustainability. The journey was aided with recourse to international and regional trends where it has been firmly established that environmental pollution prevents persons from enjoying their inalienable human rights. The first chapter identified the importance of this approach given the high rate of persistent environmental pollution in Nigeria which the common law remedies and regulatory frameworks failed to curb so that it became necessary for victims of environmental abuse to have a fundamental right to environmental protection which they could enforce in a Court of law. Thus, the rights-based approach becomes a medium to enhance access to environmental justice.

The second chapter evaluated the problems of environmental degradation in consideration of its effect on the health and life of man. It further looked at the concept of environmental justice as well as its various principles in the light of the Nigerian situation where environmental justice has not been given due consideration by the government because of its implications on economic development. Subsequently, it was acknowledged that in order to facilitate access to environmental justice, participation rights, access to information, amongst others, are indispensable. This chapter further traced the origin of environmental rights and discussed its imprecise nature. It also appraised the rights-based approach and considered decisions of international, regional and domestic courts, where it was utilised to facilitate environmental justice. Also, the problems associated with it were discussed, to which recommendations are proffered in this present chapter.

The third chapter examined **section 20** of the **Constitution** as well as other provisions under the constitution that recognise environmental protection. It was observed that the provision of **section 6(6)(c)** of the **Constitution** acts as an impediment to the enforcement of the right. That section does not however affect other arms of government (legislature and executive) from realizing the provisions of Chapter II. Recent judicial decisions on Chapter II are to the effect that the mere fact that a provision under the law is made non-justiciable does not deny it of enforcement, since by an enactment of legislation dealing with the same subject matter, a non-justiciable provision can be made justiciable. Hence, the enactment of the African Charter into the municipal order in Nigeria paved the way for the enforcement of environmental rights in

Nigeria. That charter was applied in *Gbemre v. Shell*³⁰⁰ and *Centre for Oil Pollution Watch*,³⁰¹ to enforce the environmental rights of members of the affected communities. Those cases show judicial activism on the part of the judges to realise the right, by construing **section 20** in the light of the African Charter's provisions and other inalienable rights guaranteed under **Chapter IV** of the Constitution. In addition, the recognition of environmental rights by the regional courts and at the international level was looked at.

The fourth chapter made a detailed analysis of environmental rights enforcement by the court. It recognised the change of attitude of the court following the decision in *Shell v. Farah*,³⁰² where adequate compensation was awarded and an order for remediation of the polluted environment was made. However, it was not until the High Court's decision in *Gbemre v. Shell*,³⁰³ that a nexus was created between environmental degradation and human rights violation. It finally became the law in Nigeria that there is a right to environmental protection with the Supreme Court's decision in *Centre for Oil Pollution Watch v. NNPC*.³⁰⁴ The chapter also embarked on a comparative analysis with India, where it was discovered that the Indian Courts have blazed the trail since the early 1990s by enforcing the right to environmental protection through the rights to life provision under its constitution. Lessons were derived for Nigeria from that jurisdiction, especially as regards the Court's attitude in giving little regard to the economic benefits of a venture when it tends to affect the environment. It was however acknowledged that, unlike Nigeria, the government of India is not directly a stakeholder in mining activities, so that external influence on Courts' decisions is not an issue. Also, the chapter illustrates the various mediums by which the right to environment can be upheld in Nigeria, with the Courts playing the major role and other government agencies performing secondary (but critical) functions.

5.1. Recommendations

The whole essence of this research project is to justify the necessity of a rights-based approach as a *sine qua non* to the full realisation of environmental justice in Nigeria. Albeit, various factors militate the effectiveness of this approach especially concerning the state of affairs of the country which was looked at in preceding chapters. Central to the proffered recommendations is the need for the justiciability of the right to environmental protection under

³⁰⁰ (2005) AHRLR 151.

³⁰¹ (2019) 5 NWLR (Pt. 1666) 518.

³⁰² (1995) 3 NWLR.

³⁰³ *Supra*.

³⁰⁴ *Supra*.

the Nigerian Constitution. The other recommendations are made to facilitate the utilization of environmental rights for environmental justice.

5.1.1. Justiciability of the Right to Environmental Protection

Nigeria is a democratic society, and as such the realization of fundamental human rights is a key component of its affairs. Environmental degradation serves as a bar to the enjoyment of these rights for all people since an unsafe environment would endanger the life and general livelihood of the citizens. Thus, there is no justifiable reason why environmental rights should continue to remain non-justiciable. This recommendation is enforced by the enactment of the **African Charter** into law in Nigeria especially the provision of **section 24** which guarantees the right to environmental protection. Similarly, Nigeria is bound to give effect to the right under **Chapter IV** of the **Constitution** due to being a signatory of various treaties that recognises the right to environmental protection. Hence, based on the principle of *pacta sunt servanda*, the government cannot continue to act in total disregard of international treaties.³⁰⁵ Similarly, the National Assembly by virtue of **section 13** of the **Constitution** is required to give effect to environmental protection since they are not barred by the provision of **section 6(6)(c)** of the **Constitution**. By this, the National Assembly can foster the amendment of the Constitution for this recommendation to be effected. The justiciability of this right would solidify the correlation between economic development and environmental protection in Nigeria³⁰⁶ to ensure the sustainable use of natural resources.³⁰⁷

5.1.2. Judicial Activism and Expansive Interpretation of the Constitution

This recommendation is required pending the justiciability of the right to environmental protection. Indeed, the Nigerian Courts have been proactive in recent years by giving effect to environmental rights through the corpus of other rights, especially the rights to life. However, the shortcoming of this approach is that the realization of environmental rights would be dependent on other rights so that if no right guaranteed under the Constitution or African Charter is violated in the course of environmental pollution, a victim of environmental abuse would be without remedy. Thus, it is recommended that the court in Nigeria should be more proactive in making the right to environmental protection a part and parcel of the right to life, rather than merely being dependent on it. This has been the attitude of the Indian and Pakistan Courts, as was demonstrated in the case of *Shela Zia v. Water and Power Development*

³⁰⁵ O. Awolowo, "Environmental Rights and Sustainable Development in Nigeria", *OIDA International Journal of Sustainable Development, Ontario International Development Agency, Canada* ISSN 1923-6654. Available online at <http://www.ssrn.com/link/OIDA-Intl-Journal-Sustainable-Dev.htm> (accessed 10 August, 2021).

³⁰⁶ *Ibid.*

³⁰⁷ Till this is done, those oil corporations that pollute the environment with impunity may not take the court decisions that have guaranteed the right to environment seriously. The constitution is a stamp on finality.

Authority,³⁰⁸ where it was held that the right to life included a right to live in a clean environment. There is no reason why individuals and communities in Nigeria should not be able to enforce the right to a clean environment under the fundamental human rights provision in **section 33** of the Nigerian constitution.³⁰⁹ Even though the High Court in *Gbemre v. Shell*³¹⁰ followed this same line of thinking by making a declaratory order that the constitutionally guaranteed fundamental rights to life and dignity of human persons, inevitably includes the right to clean poison-free, pollution-free and healthy environment, the Supreme Court did not follow suit in *Centre for Oil Pollution Watch*.³¹¹

5.1.3. Legislative Reforms of Environmental Laws

Environmental laws are very important for the realisation of the right to environmental protection. However, the current regulatory frameworks on environmental protection are plagued with many deficiencies. These deficiencies are in fact amongst the justification for a rights-based approach to environmental protection. Thus, it is recommended that to enhance enforcement of the set rules and regulations, stiffer sanctions should be prescribed under environmental laws, so as to have a deterrent effect on members of the society and the person responsible for the violation. In addition, the many laws on environmental protection in Nigeria should be consolidated to ensure compliance and prevent overlapping functions of agencies.³¹² Moreover, many environmental laws in Nigeria have not proved to be effective in realizing the purpose for which they were enacted. For instance, the **EIA Act** has failed to ensure the assessment of the likely impact of private and public projects likely to endanger the environment.³¹³ Experience has shown that most producers and handlers of toxic waste are slow to comply with the impact assessment provisions unless extreme measures of enforcement are applied. It is thus recommended that the ameliorative provisions³¹⁴ should be more aggressively enforced.³¹⁵

Also, the **NESREA Act** and **Harmful Waste (Special Criminal Provisions) Act** have not been able to deal with the consequences of toxic waste exposure in Nigeria.³¹⁶ It is thus

³⁰⁸ PLD 1994 SC A16.

³⁰⁹ *Supra* note 305.

³¹⁰ *Supra*.

³¹¹ The Court in this case made the right to environmental protection dependent on the right to life guaranteed under the Constitution and the African Charter, but not inherent in the right to life.

³¹² This recommendation was followed by Lagos State in 2017 by repealing several environmental laws that were in existence and bringing them under the auspices of the newly enacted **Lagos State Environmental Management and Protection Law**.

³¹³ T. O. Ilegbune, "Environmental Law and Enforcement" in *Environmental Law and Policy*, *Simpson and Fagbohun*, (Lagos Law Centre, LASV, 1998), pp. 205 – 210.

³¹⁴ Such provisions are mainly administrative in nature, e.g., license withdrawal, imposition of fines and plant closures.

³¹⁵ Ogbodo, Dr. S. Gozie, "Environmental Protection in Nigeria: Two Decades after the Koko Incident," *Annual Survey of International & Comparative Law*: Vol. 15: Iss. 1, Article 2, (2009). Available online at <http://digitalcommons.law.ggu.edu/annlsurvey/vol15/iss1/2> (accessed 10 August, 2021).

³¹⁶ *Ibid*.

recommended that the duty of care concept³¹⁷ should be infused into these legislations in assessing the liability of all producers and handlers of waste³¹⁸ similar to the United Kingdom (UK) Environmental Protection Act (EPA), 1990.³¹⁹ The duty of care principle serves the following purposes;³²⁰ to prevent the commission of one of the statutory offences; to prevent the escape of waste; to ensure any transfer of waste is transferred to an authorized person; to ensure that a written description goes with the waste so that others can comply with the duty. By these recommendations, teeth would be added to those statutes.

5.1.4. Public Enlightenment and Education

This recommendation is borne out of the fact that many members of society are ignorant of the process for which their environmental rights can be enforced. In addition, the rights-based approach can only serve as a means to ensure environmental protection, when those persons who are victims of environmental abuse are well aware of their rights. This is even more needed in Nigeria where the most knowledgeable are the violators or potential violators, while the uneducated are victims of these violations.³²¹ Hence, McGath posits thus:³²² *“Knowledge...is crucial for effective...litigation to protect the environment. The environmental legal system is often complex, convoluted and illogically structured with multiple legislative schemes and government administrators. Complex issues of law and fact commonly arise with which ordinary members of the community are unfamiliar.”*³²³

5.1.5. Civil Society Participation

Civil societies include persons, institutions, and organizations that have the goal of advancing or expressing a common purpose through ideas, actions, and demands on governments.³²⁴ It is an important institution in any democratic society because it preaches the message of justice and goodwill for all people. In the context of environmental protection, they play a crucial role by conducting research to facilitate policy development, building institutional capacity, and facilitating independent dialogue to help people live more sustainable lifestyles.³²⁵ Additionally, Non-Governmental Organisations (NGOs) can help vocalise the interests of

³¹⁷ Established in the case of *Donoghue v. Stevenson* (1932) A. C. 562.

³¹⁸ **Section 34** of the UK EPA 1990 states that, Producers and handlers of waste are all those operating in the stream of waste i.e., those who import, produce, carry, keep, treat or dispose of controlled waste.

³¹⁹ Which came into force from April, 1992. Culled from *Supra* note 315.

³²⁰ R. Malcolm, “A Guidebook to Environmental Law,” 1994, p.204.

³²¹ T. Madebwe, “A rights-based approach to environmental protection: The Zimbabwean experience”, *Op. cit.* p. 122.

³²² Although he referred only to public interest litigation, it can still apply to other forms of actions filed in Court on account of environmental right violation.

³²³ C. McGrath, “Flying foxes, dams and whales: Using Federal Environmental Laws in the Public Interest” (2008) 25 *Environmental and Planning Law Journal* 324.

³²⁴ C. L. Jean, A. Arato. 1992. “Civil Society and Political Theory”, Cambridge, MA: MIT Press.

³²⁵ R. Al Mubarak, T. Alam, “The Role of NGOs in Tackling Environmental Issues”, April 26, 2012. Available online at <https://www.mei.edu/publications/role-ngos-tackling-environmental-issues> (accessed 25, August 2021).

victims of environmental degradation not well-represented in policymaking. In Nigeria, much reliance has been placed on international NGOs to aid victims of environmental abuse. A plethora of environmental matters that have emanated from Nigeria, both at the local and institutional levels was initiated by foreign NGOs.³²⁶ The implication of this is that the Government would continue to exercise a lack of political will on environmental protection since it is yet to be challenged by the people or at least their representatives. It is thus recommended that Nigerian NGOs be actively involved in decisions that concern the environment so as to ensure that only favourable environmental policies are put in place by the Government.

5.1.6. Establishment of Environmental Courts

Across the globe, environmental courts have gained currency due to the growth of new environmental laws and principles across the world, and the dissatisfaction of the public with the traditional judicial forum.³²⁷ Environmental courts as a specialised Court, would entertain environmental matters and facilitate for better enforcement of environmental laws in the country.³²⁸ In addition, it would ensure a quick response to the needs of the environment and popularize environmental rights.³²⁹ Commenting on environmental Courts, Pring and Pring noted that, “these new specialized bodies are rapidly changing not only traditional judicial and administrative structures but the very manner in which environmental disputes are resolved.”³³⁰

Indeed this would not be the first time Nigeria would have to establish a specialised Court. In 2007, the government established that National Industrial Court specialising in civil matters relating to any labour, employment, trade union, industrial relations, and matters arising from the workplace, the condition of service, including health, safety, welfare of labour, employee, worker and matter connected therewith.³³¹ It is thus submitted that if a specialised Court was established for labour matters, even more so for environmental matters a specialised Court is required in Nigeria.

5.1.7. Funding and Training

³²⁶ For instance, the case of *Wiwa v. Royal Dutch Pet. (Supra)*, the action was instituted by the Center for Constitutional Rights (CCR) and co-counsel from EarthRight International under the Alien Torts Act in United States. Also, the communication of *SERAC v. Nigeria (Supra)* brought before the African Commission on Human Rights by The Social and Economic Rights Action Center and the Center Economic, and Social Rights.

³²⁷ I. Thiaw, ‘Foreward’ in G. Pring and C. Pring, *Greening Justice: Creating and Improving Environmental Courts and Tribunals (The Access Initiative of the World Resources Institute: U.S, 2009)* p. iii. Culled from U. Naphtali, “Green Courts in Nigeria: Strengthening Environmental Litigation and Access to Green Justice”, *Lambert Academic Publishing*, 2019.

³²⁸ H. Ijaiya, O. T. Joseph, “Rethinking Environmental Law Enforcement in Nigeria”, *Beijing Law Review*, 2014, 5, 306-321. Available online at <http://dx.doi.org/10.4236/blr.2014.54029> (accessed 11 August, 2021).

³²⁹ *Ibid.*

³³⁰ *Supra* note 327.

³³¹ **Section 7** of the **National Industrial Court Act, 2007.**

This recommendation is vital because environmental protection agencies have not been able to execute their functions properly and efficiently owing to the lack of economic and intellectual resources that would enable them to do so. It is thus recommended that adequate funds should be allocated by the Government at all levels to enable them to execute projects that are geared towards the improvement of the environment. Moreover, the government should equip environmental protection agencies with the requisite knowledge and skill needed to carry out functions provided under the law. For instance, NESREA has been given wide regulatory functions under the Act to set rules and standards concerning environmental use. This Agency would thus be required to know the intricacies of legislative competence so that the regulations do not stand the risk of being voided in a court of law upon conflicting with federal legislation or even the Constitution on that subject matter.³³² Similarly, the Agency should be made well aware of international best practices so that the regulations and standards would reflect those tenets and principles needed for sustainability.

5.2. Conclusion

This research project has been able to examine environmental protection through the ambit of human rights. It considered the problems environmental abuse poses on human life and the failure of the existing legal framework to attend to the plight of victims of such abuse. From this paper, a critical analysis of environmental rights in Nigeria was made, and several issues acting as an impediment to the full realisation of the right were discussed. It is only hoped that there would be a change in the attitude of the government towards a safe and healthy environment since the lack of political will on their part would render this research project an exercise in futility. The government of Nigeria are thus advised to take a cue from the words of Ban ki-moon (the former UN secretary-general), “*Saving our planet, lifting people out of poverty, advancing economic growth... these are one and the same fight. We must connect the dots between climate change, water scarcity, energy shortages, global health, food security, and women’s empowerment. Solutions to one problem must be solutions for all.*”³³³

³³² G. O. Amokaye, *Environmental Law and Practice in Nigeria*. Lagos: *Op. cit.* p.129.

³³³ Ban Ki-moon address to the 66th General Assembly of the United Nations: “We the Peoples”, 21 September 2011. Available online at <https://www.un.org/sg/en/content/sg/speeches/2011-09-21/address-66th-general-assembly-we-peoples> (accessed 11 August 2021).

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